

Water modelling system upgrade and software support services

Intermediate report

Client: Lithuanian Environmental protection agency

Agreement # 28T-2020-43 of 04-Aug-2020

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Procesu analīzes un izpētes centrs

SUMMARY

The intermediate report provide the description of activities done and results obtained within the first half-year of the project. It provides description (1) the renewal of the modelling system, (2) the upgrade of the data of the modelling system, (3) adding new functionality to the system – capacity of modelling small water bodies and use of agrometeorological weather stations’ and rainfall radar data.

Report is written in English, it contains 116 pages, 69 figures, 12 tables and 6 references.

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1. INTRODUCTION

This is the first intermediate report in the framework of the Contract #28T-2020-43 of 04-Aug-2020 between the Lithuanian Environmental protection agency (Client) and “SIA Procesu analizēs un izpētes centrs” (Consultant).

According to the Contract the first intermediate report is prepared within 6 months from the starting date of the Contract (22-Sep-2020).

The aim of the project is the upgrade of the SWAT water quantity and quality modelling system of Lithuania and providing the related software support services, i.e. operational support during the initial phase of the application of the updated system.

As such, the project is divided into 3 stages:

- The first stage (Sep/2020-Mar/2021) is the upgrade of the modelling system and renewal of its input data.
- The second stage (Mar/2021-Sep/2021) is the calibration of the upgraded modelling system and development an extensive script library for its usage.
- The third stage (Sep/2021-Sep/2022) is the support of the upgraded modelling system and its software elements.

According to the Contract the inception report PAIC (2020) described the planned activities and timing for the implementation of the project activities; it included agreed modifications of the Terms of reference of the project.

The goals of the first stage were

1. The renewal – change of the background technologies – of the modelling system (ToR 1.1) – moving from Python 2 to Python 3 (ToR 1.1.2), SWAT2012 to the SWAT+ (ToR 1.1.1&1.1.3) and transfer of the ArcGIS GIS functions to open source GIS libraries (ToR 1.1.4). The description of these tasks are given in the Sections of the Chapter 2.
2. The upgrade of the data of the modelling system is described in the Chapter 3:
 - a. Upgrade of the spatial division - river network and respective basin data (ToR 2.1) is described in Section 3.1;
 - b. Upgrade of the rest of the modelling system input data (ToR 2.2) is described in the subsections of the Section 3.2.
3. Adding of new functionality – ability to model small water bodies – to the modelling system (ToR 1.2) is described in the Chapter 4.
4. Adding rainfall radar data as precipitation input data to the model (ToR 1.3) is considered in the Chapter 5..

Together with this report the project results (preprocessed data, geodatabases, program code, SWAT+ setups) are prepared in electronic format (listed in Annex).

2. RENEWAL OF MODELLING SYSTEM

2.1. Change of background technologies

There are several prerequisites for renewal of technologies used in water quality modelling system:

- The existing water quality modelling system of the Client is based on SWAT2012 software which has no longer been developed (supported) and is being replaced with SWAT+.
- The Python programming language and its tools develops rapidly, with new generation Python 3 (and a large amount of free libraries) available.
- The open access GIS systems, databases and libraries gain popularity, continuously replacing ArcGIS GIS system.

The following technologies are chosen for the renewal of the modelling system:

- Database: PostgreSQL version 13.1-1¹ or later with spatial extension PostGIS version 3.0.3 or later for Windows-x64² is required for storing all modelling system data instead of ArcGIS Geodatabase.
- Python 3.8.6: WinPython64-3.8.6.0cod.exe³ portable distribution of the Python programming language for Windows-x64 is used instead of ArcGIS built-in Python 2 programming language for all the scripts forming the modelling system.
- Geospatial information system QGIS with GDAL libraries⁴ for operations with geospatial data is used instead of ArcGIS.
- SWAT+ version rev. 60.5.2⁵ released on 11-Mar-2021 is used instead of SWAT2012.
- SWAT+ Editor⁶ v 2.0.1 source code.

The structure of the modelling system data and tools are described in Section 2.2 while the renewed scripts of the modelling system – in Section 2.3.

The required background tools and systems mentined in this Section are installed by running batch file.

¹ <https://www.postgresql.org/download/>

² <https://postgis.net/install/>

³ <https://winpython.github.io/>

⁴ osgeo4w-setup-x86_64.exe from <https://trac.osgeo.org/osgeo4w/>

⁵ <https://swatplus.gitbook.io/docs/installation>

⁶ <https://bitbucket.org/swatplus/swatplus.editor/src/master/>

2.2. Structure of data and script

2.2.1. Structure of scripts

The structure of the modelling system data and the blocks of the system software (script) are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Elements of the modelling system.

In general, the system developed and documented in AAPC&PAIC(2014), Chapter VI-I, is renewed using the new technologies listed in Section 2.1. The modelling system principles are the same as in Section 3.1 of AAPC&PAIC(2014).

1. The initial input data are manually (or with a help of proprietary scripts outside the modelling system) processed forming the harmonised input dataset (text, raster files and PostgreSQL database). The further data processing is performed by Python script *main.py*.
2. The geospatial operations with the harmonised dataset are performed with module *GISoperations.py*, forming the extended input data set. Geospatial operations are described in Section 3.2 of AAPC&PAIC(2014).
3. Module *sqliteSetup.py* creates SWAT+ Editor setups from the input data.
4. Module *write_files.py* uses SWAT+ Editor API to creat SWAT+ setups.

5. Module *calculations.py* performs the runs of SWAT+.

Water quality model preparation process is designed to be fully automated. The system of the Python scripts that perform the generation of the SWAT+ setups is included in the electronic deliverables. The functionality of the main scripts is described in Section 2.3 dealing with the model preparation process. In this Section we provide the overall scheme of developed scripts as well as their list.

The hierarchy of the Python scripts used in the system is given below, while the structure of folders of the system is described in Section 2.2.2. Two scripts are on the top of the hierarchy:

- **Settings.py** – contains the description of the information used by the SWAT water quality modeling system as well as links to all the input data and intermediate result locations needed for other scripts of the system. The detailed description of the contents of **Settings.py** is given in Section 2.2.3.
- **Main.py** – contains the sequence and parameter references needed to run the other scripts during the automated preparation of modeling system. **Main.py** is divided into two parts – „geospatial” and „database”. It invokes all other scripts to run them sequentially as well as provides the necessary iterations through the Watersheds (setups) of the modeling system for database scripts. Thus, this script is running the sequence of model preparation described in Section 2.3.

The rest of the scripts may be divided as (a) the ones processing the geospatial information (their functionality is described in Section 2.3.1, and they are invoked via **GISoperations.py**), (b) the others processing the SWAT file structure and SWAT databases (their functionality is described in Section 2.3.2) and (c) the service scripts. The list of the scripts used in the system is provided below in alphabetical order:

atmosphericdeposition.py – script which creates a table of atmospheric deposition in catchments and updates the atmospheric deposition parameters in the database.

bufferstrips.py - script which creates a table of buffer strips in catchments and updates the buffer strip parameters in the database.

calculateSlopeRaster.py – script which prepares a slope raster from the DEM raster.

catchments.py – defines classes needed for holding all the information needed for creating the geometry of the modeling system: catchments, watersheds and rivers.

coefficients.py – script which defines how to change the SWAT parameters in the database.

common.py – utility which defines a set of common functions needed for conversion of data types.

config.py – configuration file referring to the executables and databases needed for other scripts.

drainage.py - script which creates a table of drainage fraction in HRUs and updates the melioration (drainage) parameters in the SWAT+ database.

GDAL_helper.py – utility module containing basic raster operations.

GISoperations.py – script through which all other geospatial scripts are called, it lists all possible GIS operations.

gw.py – script which applies initial concentrations of nutrients in the ground water.

HRU.py – utility script for data importing.

HRUrasterOps.py – script containing multiple geospatial functions needed to create HRUs.

initializeSetups.py – subroutine for preparation of the directory hierarchy of the watersheds.

initPAICSWAT.py – script which prepares all PAICSWAT related files.

lakesReservoirs.py – script which contains all operations done with lake and reservoir information.

lup.py – script which creates and updates the tables of land use update data.

managenment.py – script which calculates and updates all information associated with agricultural management practice (fertilizers, plowing, etc.).

observations.py – script used for reading observation data from respective files.

PG_helper.py – utility module containing basic operations with PostgreSQL database.

pointsources.py – script which contains all operations to read observed point source data and update it in the model.

precipCorrection.py – script containing functions needed to implement precipitation correction in the model.

prepareRuns.py – script used for creating and management of the hierarchical SWAT+ model runs in the modeling system.

regionalization.py – script containing routines to account for regionalization (hydrological regions).

riverdata.py – script containing functions needed for the calculation of river depth, width and Manning coefficient.

RunExe.py – utility script used for running executables in Python environment.

sqliteSetup.py – utility module used for creation of the SWAT+ Editor setups from the input data.

transboundary.py – script used for updating of transboundary inlets; depending on the variable of *inflowFromBelarus* in **settings.py** it takes the inflow from either measured data (if *False*) or from Belarus SWAT+ model (if *True*).

txtReader.py – utility script for reading .txt files.

wetlands.py – script for updating wetland parameters in the PND table.

2.2.2. Structure of data in modeling system

There are exits 2 main parts of the modelling system: PostgreSQL database and data represented in the file system. The database table names are given relative to database **defaultPGDB** of *settings.py*.

The folder structure of the water quality modeling system is given relative to the root folder (**MAINPATH** of *settings.py*). The folder names are defined in *settings.py* file and they are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Values of variables in *settings.py* defining the water quality modeling systems.

Path	Name
c:\WQMS	MAINPATH
\lib	pyPAICSWAT
\py	LIBRARYPATH
\bin	binPath
\swatplus.editor	swatplus_editor_source
\projects	
\LTSWAT2020	projectDir
\Data	dataDir
\Observations	
\Pointsources	
\Rasters	
\Scripts	
settings.py	
main.py	
\Watersheds	setupsDir
....	
\BYSWAT2020	projectDir
...

- Folder **pyPAICSWAT** (default value *lib*) contains the utility software modules:
 - The python modules are placed in folder **LIBRARYPATH** (default value *lib/py*).
 - The executable modules are placed in folder **binPath** (default value *lib/bin*).
 - SWAT+ Editor source code is placed in folder **swatplus_editor_source** (default value *lib/swatplus.editor*)
- Folders **projectDir** contain the SWAT+ setups:
 - Subfolder *Scripts* contains the main script module (*main.py*) and the settings module (*settings.py*) configured for the respective SWAT+ setup.
 - Subfolder *Data* contains SWAT+ setup specific data

- Pointsources
- Rasters
- Subfolder **setupsDir** (default value *Watersheds*) contains the setups of SWAT+ models.

The above folder structure of SWAT setups should correspond to the values of the variables defining the directory structure in the corresponding files *settings.py*:

1. **projectDir** must be set to the root folder of the respective modelling system.
2. **setupsDir** must be set to folder where setups of SWAT+ models will be located. By default it is a folder *Watersheds* relative to **projectDir**.
3. **dataDir** must be set to folder where the input data is located.

The water quality modeling system is electronically delivered as a data archive. Un-archiving of it creates a folder structure in **MAINPATH**. The water quality modeling system is generated automatically by executing the script *main.py* from folders **projectDir** /*Scripts*.

2.2.3. Structure of information in Settings.py

The file *Settings.py* contains information and links to all of the input/output data and intermediate result locations needed for other scripts. Each water quality modeling system has its respective *Settings.py* file. The input/output data and other parameters are assigned to the variables of the *Settings.py*:

1. The variables defining the file names of input data.
2. The variables defining the file names of output data.
3. The default values of numerical (or text) variables.
4. The default values of parameters defining the field names of the input files (databases).
5. The values of variables defining the executables and configuration files.
6. The variables defining the structure of the modeling system.

The contents of this file, i.e. the description of the water quality modeling system is given below:

1. Description of the digital elevation model data.
 - a. Variable *DEMFile* is set to the location of the digital elevation raster. This raster should contain one raster band with Z values of topography. Default value of the variable is **dataDir** + "Rasters/dem_5m".
 - b. Variable *SlopeFile* is set to the location of the topography slope raster. This raster could be calculated by the function *HRUrasterOps.calculateSlopeRaster*. Default value of the variable is set to **dataDir**+ "Rasters/slope_5m.tif".
 - c. Variable *SlopeClasses* is a list of slopes (in percent rise!) used for defining slope classes. List should contain a list containing ranges of slope classes and class number as a list of python types [(startvalue1, endvalue1, classnumber1),...]. By default there are 2 slope classes 0.0 – 4.0 % is a slope class 1, and >4.0% is slope class 2.
(*SlopeClasses*=[(4.0,99999,2),(0.0,4.0,1)])
 - d. Variable *slopeClassRaster* represents a slope class raster file that will be prepared for classification of HRUs. Default value of this variable is **dataDir**+ "Rasters/slopeclasses.tif".
2. Description of the landuse geospatial data (class *LandUse*).
 - a. Field *TableShapes* contains the location of the **defaultPGDB** table representing landuse. This file should contain at least an attribute *LUCODE* representing the landuse name. Default value of this variable is (*landuse, landuse*)
 - b. Variable *LUvsSWATTable* contains a location of the **defaultPGDB** table of remapping of the original landuse classes to SWAT landuse classes. This table should contain at least two attributes (1) *globalcode* – the

- landuse name corresponding to the landuses in landuse feature class; (2) *SWATCODE* – the SWAT landuse name corresponding to the names in the tables *crop* and *urban* from SWAT2012.mdb (maximum 4 characters long). Default value of this variable is (***landuse, globallookup***).
- c. Variable *Raster* represents a landuse raster file that will be prepared for the classification of HRUs. Default value of this variable is **dataDir**+ "Rasters/LUraster.tif".
 - d. Variable *TABLENAME_RASTER_SWAT_ID_LOOKUP* contains a location of the **defaultPGDB** *landuse* shema table of remapping of the SWAT landuse classes to pixel values (*FIELDNAME_RASTER_ID*) of the raster. Default value ***landuse_swat_raster_lookup***.
 - e. Variables *FIELDNAME_LANDUSENAME_LU*, *FIELDNAME_LANDUSENAME_RM*, *FIELDNAME_SWATLUNAME* provides a possibility for user to enter the fieldnames used for *LUCODE*, *globalcode* and *SWATCODE*.
 - f. Variable *TABLENAME_RASTER_LUGROUPS_ID_LOOKUP* contains a location of the **defaultPGDB** temporary table (for debug purpose only)
3. Description of the soil geospatial data.
 - a. Variable *SoilFile* contains the location of the **defaultPGDB** table representing the soil classes. This table should contain at least an attribute *SoilCode* representing the soil name. Default value of this variable is (***soil, union***).
 - b. Variable *SoilvsSWATTable* contains the location of the table of remapping of the original soil classes into the SWAT soil types. This table should contain at least two attributes (1) *DetailedCode* – the soil name corresponding to *SoilCode* in the soil feature class and (2) *SWATCODE* – the SWAT+ soil name corresponding to the names in table *usersoil* from ***SWAT2012DB*** *schema*. Default value of this variable is (***soil, globallookup***).
 - c. Variable *SoilRasterFile* is a name of the soil raster file that will be prepared for classification of HRUs. Default value of this variable is **dataDir** + "Rasters/soilraster.tif".
 - d. Variable *SoilFileVars* provides possibility for user to enter the fieldnames used for *SoilCode*, *DetailedCode* and *SWATCODE*.
 4. Subbasin and watershed definition data block provides geospatial data of catchments and river segments, catchment connection to watersheds, river network connectivity, outlets and inlets.
 - a. We use the following meanings (definitions):
 - i. **Subbasin** is a polygonal entity representing one river catchment and eventually one LSU and aquifer in SWAT+ setup.
 - ii. **River segment** is a polyline representing main river in one subbasin.

- iii. **River node** is a point that is placed on either of the ends of a river segments.
 - iv. **Watershed** is a collection of spatially connected subbasins representing one river basin that corresponds to one SWAT+ setup.
 - v. Two level naming of watersheds is provided allowing to group them into **Basins**.
 - vi. **Outlet** is an object that is placed on any external outflows from the river network. Outlets should be placed on all outflows.
 - vii. **Inlet** is an object at the external inflows into the river network.
 - viii. **External catchment** is a representing additional area outside the modelling domain that is not directly modeled, but rather accounted by increased area of receiving catchment.
 - ix. **Water transfer** is an object which allows for [fractional] water transfer from a predefined outlet to predefined river segment.
- b. The following variables are used for definition of rivers, subbasins and watersheds:
- i. Location of the subbasin table is provided by variable *CatchmentFile*. Default value of it is (*catchments,catchments*). One entity of the file should correspond to one SUBBASIN. Subbasins should fill all modeling domain (Lithuania territory). They should not overlap, and boundaries of the neighbouring catchments should topologically correspond to each other. Each subbasin should correspond to only one river segment. Integer attribute *CatchmentID* must be present, and it must correspond to unique catchment identifier.
 - ii. Location of polyline feature class representing river segments is provided by variable *RiverSegmentFile*. Default value of this variable is (*catchments,riversegments*). Polyline segment direction should have the same direction as river flow. Rivers should be split at catchment boundaries. Only one node could be placed at each particular river confluence or splitting point. Following attributes must be present in the *RiverSegmentFile*:
 1. *segmentID* – an unique integer river segment identifier of the same value as corresponding *catchmentID*.
 2. *catchmentID* – an id of the catchment that contains the river segment.
 3. *FlowTo* – a *segmentID* of the receiving river segment or *outletID* of the receiving outlet.
 4. *riverID* - an id of the river in the supplemental rivers table
 - iii. Location of the point feature class representing river nodes is provided by variable *RiverNodeFile*. Default value of this

- variable is (*catchments, nodes*). An attribute *node_ID* representing unique mode identifier must be present.
- iv. Location of the watershed table is provided by variable *WatershedTableFile*. Default value of this variable is (*catchments, watersheds*). It should contain three attributes:
 1. *watershedID* is an unique watershed identifier;
 2. *BasinName* – a basin name to which the watershed belongs;
 3. *watershedName* – name of the watershed.
 - v. Location of table that provides a grouping of the subbasins into watersheds is provided by variable *CatchmentsByWatershedTableFile*. Default value of this variable is (*catchments, catchmentsbywatersheds*). It must contain two attributes:
 1. *watershedID* – is the watershed identifier;
 2. *catchmentID* is a catchment identifier of the subbasin. One subbasin could belong to only one watershed.
 - vi. Location of a table of the outlets is provided by variable *OutletTableFile*. Default value of this variable is (*catchments, outlets*). It must contain two attributes:
 1. *outletID* – an unique integer identifier of outlet, it must be different from any of the river segment identifiers;
 2. *outletName* is the name of the outlet.
 - vii. Location of a table of external inlets is provided by variable *TransboundaryInletFile*. Default value of this variable is (*catchments , inlets*). It must contain the following three attributes:
 1. *inletID* – an unique integer identifier of inlet, it must be different from any of the river segment identifiers and any outlet identifiers;
 2. *inletName* – the name of inlet;
 3. *segmentID* – river segment identifier to which the inflow is directed.
 - viii. Location of table of external catchments is provided by variable *TransboundaryCatchmentFile*. Default value of this variable is (*catchments, transboundary*). Two attributes must be present:
 1. *catchmentID* – a catchment identifier of the subbasin with external contribution;
 2. *AddedArea* – an area in km² of the catchment located outside of the modelling domain.
 - ix. Location of the table that provides possibility of the water transfer between an outlet and another segment is given by variable *WaterTransferTable*. Default value of this variable is

(*catchments,watertransfer*). Following fields must be present in the table:

1. *transferID* – an unique identifier of an object;
 2. *outletID* – an identifier of the outlet from which the water transfer occurs;
 3. *flowTo* – a river segment identifier of the receiving river segment;
 4. *multiplier* – a coefficient by which an amount of the transferred water in outlet is multiplied.
- x. Variable *WatershedDefinitionVars* provides possibility for user to enter the fieldnames used in subbasin and watershed definition.
- xi. Variable *CatchmentIDRaster* represents a raster file containing spatially distributed catchment IDs that are prepared for classification of HRUs. Default value of this variable is **dataDir**+ "*Rasters/cmentIDraster.tif*". Database table pointed by *CatchmentFileVars* item "*TABLENAME_RASTER_SWAT_ID_LOOKUP*" contain a remapping of the catchment id to pixel values.

5. The block of HRU definition variables:
- a. Variable *globalHRUraster* shows the location of global HRU raster that is prepared by HRU definition script. Default value of this variable is **dataDir**+ "*Rasters/globalhru.tif*".
 - b. Location of a table where the mean slope of each of the HRUs is stored is provided by variable *HRUslopeTable*. Default value of this variable is (*hru,hruslopes*).
 - c. Location of a table where the mean elevation of each of the subbasins is stored is provided by a variable *CatchmentelevationTable*. Default value is (*hru,catchelev*).
 - d. Minimal HRU area in hectares is provided by a variable *HRUDefinitionVars*["*MinimalHruArea*"]. Its default value is 5.0.
6. Observation data. It should be provided in PAICSWAT format. Any observation data consists of two tab-delimited text files. Both files should be in the same directory and have the same basename. The file with extension *.sta* contains the station coordinates and names. Columns of *.sta* file are: *stationID Name X Y* (*stationID* - station integer ID, *Name* - station name, *X*, *Y* - station coordinates). Coordinates must be in a coordinate system defined by variable *defcoordSystTxt*. The file with extension *.txt* contains the daily measurements of respective parameters
- a. Meteorological parameters: a variable *WEATHER_DATA* provides the location of meteorological observation file. Its default value is **dataDir**+ "*observations/weatherdata.txt*". The following observation data

should be provided in the columns of the corresponding .txt file: *Station Date T Tmin Tmax Prec W10 RHUM Solar*:

- i. Station – a stationID corresponding to ID in .sta file,
 - ii. DATE – date in yyyy.mm.dd format,
 - iii. T, Tmin, Tmax - daily average, minimal and maximal temperatures, in degC,
 - iv. Prec - daily precipitation amount in mm/day,
 - v. W10 - daily average wind speed at 10m in m/s,
 - vi. RelHum - daily average relative humidity in %,
 - vii. Solar - daily amount of solar radiation in MJ/m²/day.
- b. Variable *Q_DATA* provides a location of daily discharge observation data. Its default value is **dataDir**+*"Observations/qobs.txt"*. Columns of the corresponding .txt file are *StationID Date Q*:
- i. StationID - stationID corresponding to ID in .sta file,
 - ii. DATE – date in in yyyy.mm.dd format,
 - iii. Q – discharge in m³/s.
- c. Variable *WQ_DATA* provides location of daily water quality observation data. Its default value is **dataDir**+*"Observations/wqobs.txt"*. Columns of the corresponding .txt file are: *StationID Date Flow SS DO BOD7 NH4-N NO2-N NO3-N N mineral N total PO4-P P total N-Org P-Org*:
- i. StationID - stationID corresponding to ID in .sta file,
 - ii. DATE – date in yyyy.mm.dd format,
 - iii. Flow – discharge in m³/s,
 - iv. The rest of columns are the values of corresponding concentrations of water quality parameters in mg/l.
- d. Variables *Q_STATIONS_CATCHMENTS* and *WQ_STATIONS_CATCHMENTS* provide the location of tables where discharge and water quality measurement station corresponding to the subbasins will be stored. Variables *OBS_FIELD_STAID* and *OBS_FIELD_STANAME* define the fieldnames of above mentioned tables corresponding to observation station ID and station name.

7. Tile drainage data.

- a. Location of a table with polygon geometry column representing meliorated territories is provided by variable *Drainage.TableShapes*. Default value of this variable is (*mel_dr10lt,melior_dissolved*).
- b. Variable *Drainage.FIELDNAME_TYPE* is the fieldname of a text attribute in *Drainage.TableShapes* containing type of drainage. Default value of this variable is 'TIPAS'.
- c. Variable *Drainage.MELIORATION_ALLOWED_TYPES* is the list of values of field *Drainage.FIELDNAME_TYPE* for which tile drainage is activated. Default values of this variable is ['D'].
- d. Variable *DrainageVars* represent parameters of tile drainage.
 - i. *DDRAIN* is a depth to subsurface drains [mm] (default – 1100.0),

- ii. *TDRAIN* is a base time to drain soil to field capacity (default – 24.0),
 - iii. *GDRAIN* is a drain tile lag (default – 24.0),
 - iv. *LIMREL* is a maximal part of HRU that is drained to activate the drainage (default - 0.05).
 - e. Variable *Drainage.raster* contains a filename of the raster that will contain the drainage data. Default value of this variable is **dataDir+"Rasters/drainage.tif"**.
 - f. Variable *Drainage.HRUDRAINAGE_TABLE* contains filename of a table where to store drainage data for each HRU. Default value of this variable is (***hru, hrudrainage***).
- 8. Atmospheric deposition data
 - a. Location of the table with polygon geometry column representing atmospheric deposition is given by a variable *ATMDEP_POLYGONS*. Default value of this variable is (***atm_deposition/atmdep2018***).
 - b. Variable *ATMDEP_BY_CATCHMENTS* provides location of the table with polygon geometry column where atmospheric deposition by catchments will be stored. Default value of this variable is (***hru/atmdepCatchm***)
 - c. Variable *ATMDEP_VARS* lists the fieldnames of *ATMDEP_POLYGONS*:
 - i. *FN_NH4_dry* - fieldname containing the dry deposition values of ammonia (mgN/m²/year). Default – “*NH4_dry*”.
 - ii. *FN_NH4_wet* - fieldname containing the wet deposition values of ammonia (mgN/m²/year). Default – “*NH4_wet*”.
 - iii. *FN_NO3_dry* - fieldname containing the dry deposition values of nitrate (mgN/m²/year). Default – “*NO3_dry*”.
 - iv. *FN_NO3_wet* - fieldname containing the wet deposition values of nitrate (mgN/m²/year). Default – “*NO3_wet*”.
 - v. *FN_precip* - fieldname containing the precipitation values as used for calculation of the wet deposition (mm/year). Default – “*precipitation*”.
 - vi. *FN_area* - fieldname containing shape area in m². Default – “*Shape_Area*”.
- 9. Buffer zone data
 - a. Variable *TableShapes* of *BufferZone* class provides the location of the table with polygon geometry representing the buffer zones. Default value of this variable is (***bufferstrips,polygons***)
 - b. Location of the feature class for storing intersection of buffer zones with catchments is provided by field *Table_BY_CATCHMENTS*. Default value of this variable is (***hru/ buffzones_catchm***).
 - c. Location of table for storing summary statistics about lengths and areas of buffer strip polygons by catchments is provided by a field

Table_STAT_BY_CATCHMENTS = ("hru","buffzones_stat"). Default value of this variable is (***hru***, ***buffzones_stat***).

- d. The field *COEFFICIENT* of *BufferZone* class is the value by which an average width of the buffer zone is multiplied to obtain the *FILTERW* parameter of *MGT* table. Default value 0.05.

10. Administrative county data

- a. Variable *countiesFC* provides a table with polygon geometry column containing administrative county boundaries (default value is (***counties***, ***counties***)). Variable *countiesIDField* contains the field name of unique integer county identifier. Default value is "*KODAS*".
- b. Variable *countiesraster* provides file name of raster of county identifiers that will be prepared by script. Default value is ***dataDir***+ "*Rasters/counties.tif*".
- c. Variable *countiesHRU* contains file name of raster where correspondence of HRUs to counties is stored. Default value is ***dataDir***+ "*Rasters/combi_cohru.tif*".

11. River parameter data

- a. River slope
 - i. Variable *nodeElevationFile* contains the name of a table where node elevations will be stored. Node elevations are used to calculate river slope. Default value of variable is (***hru***/***node_elevation***).
 - ii. Variable *RiverSlopeBounds* defines minimal and maximal allowed river slope. Default value (*0.0001*, *0.1*).
- b. River width
 - i. Variable *GDR10LTPolygons* contains name of a table with polygon geometry column *PLOTAI* of database *GDR10LT*. Default value of variable is (***gdr10lt***, ***plotai***).
 - ii. Variable *GDRintersectCatchments* is the name of a table with polygon geometry column where intersection of *GDR10LTPolygons* with subbasin polygon feature class will be stored. Default value of this variable is (***ivers***, ***gdr_water_catchments***).
 - iii. Variable *riverWidthGDR_table* contains a name of the table where the calculated river width will be stored. Default value of this variable is (***ivers***, ***river_width***). Variable *fieldnameWidth* is the name of the field where the river width will be stored.
- c. River depth
 - i. Variable *riverDepthGrid* contains the name of grid of river depths. Default value of this variable is ***dataDir***+ "*Rasters/bath_5m.tif*".

- ii. Variable *riverFPPolygons* contains the name of table with polygon geometry column of the rivers obtained from grid of river depths. Default value of this variable is (*rivers, polygon*).
 - iii. Variable *riverPolyCatchmentIntersect* contains the name of table with polygon geometry column where river polygon intersection with subbasin polygon feature class will be stored. Default value of this variable is (*rivers, riverpolyintersectcatchm*)
 - iv. Variable *segmentDepthTable* contains name of the table where river segment depth information will be stored. Default value of this variable is (*river,segmentdepth*).
- d. River Manning's coefficients
- i. Variable *ManningCoefFile* is name of a table with polyline geometry column where Manning's coefficient values from the FLOOD project is stored. Default value is (*rivers,manning*). Field name where Manning's coefficient is stored is provided by variable *fieldNameManningCoef*. Default value of it is "n".
 - ii. Variable *segmentManningtable* is the name of a table where Manning's coefficients for river segments will be stored. Default value of this variable is (*rivers,segmentmanningcoef*).
 - iii. Default value of Manning's coefficient is stored in a variable *riverDefaults["defaultManningCoef"]*. It is 0.03.

12. Data related to management practices and fertilization

- a. Field *PLANTFERT* of *Fert* class provides a location of a table name of the plant related fertilization table. This table must contain the following fields:
- i. *SWAT_ID* (integer) – SWAT code of the plant, corresponding to crop table's field *SNAM*.
 - ii. *Plant_Name* (text) – name of the plant.
 - iii. *Method* (integer) – method number for calculation of the fertilization amount (1 or 2). Blank may be left in case if fertilization is not calculated for the particular plant.
 - iv. *Std_yield* (double) – standard yield for the plant (tons/ha/year).
 - v. *N_Demand* (double) – nitrogen demand (kgN/ha/year).
 - vi. *P_Demand* – phosphorus demand (kgP/ha/year).
 - vii. *Preplant_N* – preplant nitrogen amount (kgN/ha/year).
 - viii. *Preplant_P* – preplant phosphorus amount (kgP/ha/year).
- b. Field *LIVESTOCK* of *Fert* class contains the location of the MS Access database and tablename of the table storing the number of livestock units in the counties. This table must contain the following fields:
- i. *Kodas* (integer) – unique integer county identifier that corresponds to the *countiesIDField* of *countiesFC*.

- ii. *livestock_units* (double) – number of standard animal units in county.
- c. Field *PLANNEDIYIELD* of *Fert* class contains location of the MS Access database and tablename of table storing yield by county and crop. It must contain following fields:
 - i. *SWAT_ID* (integer) - SWAT code of the plant, corresponding to the crop table's field *SNAM*.
 - ii. *Kodas* (integer) - unique integer county identifier that corresponds to *countiesIDField* of *countiesFC*.
 - iii. *Planned_yield* – yield amount in tons/ha/year.
- d. Field *PLANTMGT* of *Fert* class provides the location of the MS Access database and tablename of table storing management practices for each of the SWAT landuse codes. This table must be in *MSAccess* format and contain the following fields:
 - i. *SWAT_ID* (integer) - SWAT code of the landuse, corresponding to crop table's field *SNAM* or urban table's field *URBNAME*.
 - ii. *LUClass* (text) – text identifier of landuse group. Possible values are *Agricultural*, *Barren*, *Forest*, *Pasture*, *Urban*, *Water*, *Wetland*.
 - iii. *PHU* (double) – plant heat units to bring a plant to maturity. This variable applies if *LUClass* is *Agricultural*.
 - iv. *PlantHU* (double)– base zero heat units for planting. This variable applies if *LUClass* is *Agricultural*.
 - v. *HarvestHU* (double) – base zero heat units for harvest. This variable applies if *LUClass* is *Agricultural*. For winter crops it should be larger than 1.0, to indicate the next year.
 - vi. *HarvestHU2* (double)– plant heat units for harvest. This variable applies if *LUClass* is *Agricultural*.
 - vii. *P_AplHU* (double) – base zero heat units for mineral phosphorus application.
 - viii. *Tillage1*, *Tillage2*, *Tillage3*, *Tillage4* (double) – these four fields represent the base zero heat units for application of 4 types of the tillage operations. For winter crops these fields should be larger than 1.0, to indicate the next year.
 - ix. *N_AplHU1*, *N_AplHU2*, *N_AplHU3* (double) – these three fields represent base zero heat units for application of the mineral nitrogen up to 3 times per year. For winter crops value of these fields should be larger than 1.0, to indicate the next year.
 - x. *N_Amount1*, *N_Amount2*, *N_Amount3* (double) – the fields contain fractions of total mineral nitrogen application up to 3 times per year. The total sum of fractions should equal to 1.0.
 - xi. *Man_apl_HU1*, *Man_apl_HU2* (double) – these two fields represent base zero heat units for application of manure up to 2

times per year. For winter crops the values larger than 1.0 indicates the next year.

- xii. *Man_apl_amount1*, *Man_apl_amount2* (double) – the fields contain the fractions of the total manure application up to 2 times per year. The total sum of fractions should equal to 1.0.
- e. Variable *landusegroup raster* is the name of raster that will contain a spatial distribution of the landuse groups. Default value of this variable is **dataDir**+*"Rasters/lugroups.tif"*.
- f. Variable *lugroupbycountyraster* is the name of raster that will contain geospatial distribution of the landuse groups by counties. Default value of this variable is **dataDir**+*"Rasters/lugrcounty.tif"*
- g. Variable *agriculturalgroups* is the list of land use groups for agricultural land calculations and fertilization. Default value is [*"AGRICULTURAL"*, *"PASTURE"*].
- h. Variable *mineralFertilizertable* is the name of the table where calculated mineral fertilizer application per HRU will be stored. Default value of this variable is (*hru*, *fertilizer*).
- i. Variable *management_vars* is a python dictionary containing the information related to the management:
 - i. *"past_bioint"* is the initial biomass on the pastures (kg/ha). Default value of this variable is *5000.0*.
 - ii. *"past_phu"* is the number of heat units to bring the pastures to maturity (chosen larger than typical heat units per year to not mature the grass!). Default value of this variable is *3000.0*.
 - iii. *"frst_bioint"* is the default initial biomass of forests (kg/ha). Default value of this variable is *100000.0*. It is used if *FORESTBIOMASS TABLE* does not provide the information about the forest biomass for particular *SWAT ID*.
 - iv. *"frst_phu"* – is heat units to bring forests to maturity (chosen larger than typical heat units per year to not mature the trees!). Default *3000.0*.
 - v. *"ID_MineralN"* – is id of the elemental nitrogen fertilizer from *fert* table in *SWAT_DB*. Default value of this variable is *1*.
 - vi. *"ID_MineralP"* – is id of the elemental phosphorus fertilizer from *fert* table in *SWAT_DB*. Default value of this variable is *2*.
 - vii. *"ID_Manure"* – is id of the manure fertilizer from *fert* table in *SWAT_DB* (this fertilizer should have 1.0 units of total nitrogen!). Default value of this variable is *55*.
 - viii. *"ID_Tillage"* – is a python table of length 4 containing tillage identifiers for the 4 predefined tillage types corresponding to the tillage fields in *PLANTMGT_TABLE*. Default value of this variable is (*108*, *109*, *1*, *111*).
- j. Information about the large farms:

- i. Variable *largefarmsFC* is the name of the table with polygonal geometry column containing the geospatial location of “large farms” which are used for the fertilizer amount calculations. Default value of this variable is (*landuse,large_farms*)
 - ii. Variable *largefarmsraster* is the name of raster that will contain geospatial location of “large farms”. Default value of this variable is **dataDir**+*"Rasters/rlargefarms.tif"*.
 - iii. Variable *hrulargefarms* is the name of the raster storing information of the large farms per each of the HRUs. Default value of this variable is **dataDir**+*"Rasters/hrufarms.tif"*.
 - iv. Variable *largefarmFertilizerCoef* is a coefficient by which to multiply mineral fertilizer amount in "large farms". Default value of this variable is 1.2.
- k. Information about the fertilization regional coefficients in the *Fertilizer* class:
 - i. Field *TableShape* is the name of the table with polygonal geometry column that contains the regional multipliers to the calculated amount of the mineral fertilizer amounts. Default value of this variable is (*fert, fertcoeff*). Field name of multiplier is provided by field *Field_fertCoeff*.
 - ii. Field *TableCoeffByCatchments* is the name of the polygonal feature class where intersection of *fertilizerRegionalCoefficients* with subbasin polygons will be stored. Default value of this variable is (*hru, fertcoeffbycatchm*).
- l. Variable *FORESTBIOMASS_TABLE* provides a location of the tablename of the table containing the initial forest biomass in kg/ha for forest landuses. It must contain the following fields:
 - i. *SWAT_ID* (integer) - SWAT code of the plant, corresponding to the crop table’s field *SNAM*.
 - ii. *Biomass* (double) – forest biomass in kg/ha.

13. Initial nutrient concentration in groundwater:

- a. Variable *GW_ConcN* is a Python dictionary which contains the initial concentrations (mg/l) of nitrate in the shallow aquifer per landuse groups. Default values are:
 - i. *"AGRICULTURAL"*: 2.50
 - ii. *"PASTURE"*: 1.15
 - iii. *"FOREST"*: 1.12
 - iv. *"URBAN"*: 3.8
- b. Variable *GW_ConcP* is a Python dictionary which contains the initial concentrations (mg/l) of soluble phosphorus in the shallow aquifer per landuse groups. Default values are:
 - i. *"AGRICULTURAL"*:0.02
 - ii. *"PASTURE"*:0.05

- iii. "FOREST":0.06
- iv. "URBAN":0.04
- v. Lake and reservoir related variables.

14. Reservoir and lake data.

- a. Variable *TableShapes* of the class *LakesReserv* is the name of polygonal feature class containing the reservoir and lake data. Default value of this variable is (*catchments, lakes_reserv*) This table must contain at least the following columns:
 - i. *Snpl* - surface area at the normal water level (ha). If value of *Snpl* is zero, it is assumed that for a particular polygon *Snpl, Savl, Vnpl and Vavl* are not given.
 - ii. *Savl* - surface at the highest water level (ha).
 - iii. *Vnpl* - volume at the normal water level (in 1000 of m³).
 - iv. *Vavl* - volume of the water needed to fill the reservoir to the emergency spillway (in 1000 of m³).
 - v. *Gylis* - average depth of lake/reservoir (m). If it is zero, then it is assumed, that the average depth is not given.
 - vi. *Shape_area* – the area of lake or reservoir polygon in m², corresponding to the geometric area of a feature.
- b. Fields *Field_** of the class *LakesReserv* contains the column names of above-mentioned fields of *TableShapes*.
- c. Variable *lakesreservoirsbycatchments* is a name of the polygon feature class which will contain the intersection of the *reservoirlakefc* with the subbasin polygons. Default value of this variable is (*hru,lakesreservoirs*).
- d. Variable *reservoirParams* contains the default depth of reservoirs (used for volume calculations if volumes are not given) and default difference between the highest and normal waterlevel (used for highest volume calculations if they are not given). Default values of this variable are 3.0 and 0.3, respectively.
- e. Variable *lakeParams* contains the default depth of lakes (used for volume calculations if volumes are not given) and the default difference between the highest and normal waterlevel (used for highest volume calculations if they are not given). Default values of this variable are 2.0 and 0.2, respectively.
- f. Variable *reservoirReleasetime* is a time in days to release the reservoirs from maximum to normal level. It is used for calculation of the average daily release rate

15. Parameters for annual average precipitation correction:

- a. Variable *AnnualPrecipitationRaster* is the name of a raster containing the geospatial distribution of the annual average precipitation values. Default value of this variable is **dataDir**+ "*Rasters/Precip.TIF*".

- b. Variable *AnnualPrecipitationStationtable* is the name of a table containing the annual precipitation values for observation stations, corresponding to the stations in *WEATHER_DATA*. Default value of this variable is (*obs, statpcp*). Variable *AnnualPFieldNames* determines the field names for the station ID and the annual average precipitation.
- c. Variable *catchmentPrecipitationtable* is a name of the table where the catchment annual average precipitation will be stored. Default value of this variable is (*hru, precip_by_catch*).

16. Wetland parameters:

- a. Variable *WetlandsVars* contains:
 - i. "*wet_normD*" - average normal depth of water in the wetlands (m). Default value of this variable is 2.0.
 - ii. "*wet_maxD*" - average maximal depth of water in the wetlands (m). Default value of this variable is 3.0.
 - iii. "*WetlandLandUseIDs*" is a list of landuse codes that define a wetland. Default value of this variable is [*"WETN", "WETF"*].

17. Landuse update (*LanduseUpdate*) related variables:

- a. Field *update_fractions* contains a table name of the table where landuse update proportional fractions per cathment are stored. Default value of this variable is (*lup,lupupdate*). This table must contain the following fields:
 - i. *catchmentID* (integer) – catchment ID of subbasin as defined in *CatchmentFile*.
 - ii. *Agricultural, Barren, Forest, Pasture, Urban, Water, Wetland* (double) – these fields provide values of update fractions per each landuse group.
- b. Field *date* is a start date of landscape update (*yyyy,mm,dd*), if it is empty () then the landscape update is not applied. Default value of this variable is ().
- c. Field for preparation of the landuse update fractions:
 - i. Fields *classes_1* and *classes_2* define the names of the two polygon feature classes which define two sequential landuses. Default values of these variables are (*clc2006_lt, clc06_lt*) and (*clc2006_lt,clc18_lt*).
 - ii. Field *lup_lookup_table* is the name of the table that defines the relations between the landscape update polygons and the general landuse groups as defined by *PLANTMGT_TABLE* field *LUClass*. Default value of this variable is (*lup, luplookup*).
 - iii. Field *lupfields* defines the field names of *landuse_classes_1*, *landuse_classes_2* and *lup_lookup_table*.
 - iv. Fields *catchments_1* and *catchments_2* contain the names of the table which will contain the intersection of the

landuse_classes_1 and *landuse_classes_2* with the subbasin polygons. Default values of these variables are (*lup, corine2006*) and (*lup, corine2018*).

- v. Fields *table_1* and *table_2* are names of tables where amounts of landuse groups per subbasin will be stored.

18. Pointsource variables:

- a. Variable *PS_catchment_table* is the name of the table that will contain *catchmentID* of the subbasin for each of the pointsources. Default value of this variable is (*point_sources, ps_catchment*).
- b. Variables *Field_PS_ID* and *Field_PS_Name* are the field names of the point source integer ID and point source name in *PS_catchment_table*.
- c. Variable *PS_MONTHLY_FILE* contains the name of the monthly point source file in PAICSWAT format. Default value of this variable is **dataDir**+ "Pointsources/monthly.txt". The monthly pointsource data consists of two tab delimited text files. Both files should be in the same directory and have the same basename.
 - i. Columns of .sta file are: *pointsourceID, Name, X, Y, sourceID* (*pointsourceID* – point source integer ID, *Name* - point source name, *X,Y* - point source coordinates, *sourceID* - text identifier of point source that relates it to the original data). Coordinates must be in a coordinate system defined by the variable *defcoordSystTxt*.
 - ii. The file with extension *.txt* contains monthly point source values. Columns of this file are:
 1. *ID* – the point source integer ID as defined by *.sta* file.
 2. *DATE* – date of point source in *yyyy.mm.dd* format. Day for monthly point sources is always 15.
 3. *SS, BOD7, NO3, NO2, NH4, NTOT, PO4, PTOT, NORG, PORG* are the loads of suspended solids, BOD7, N-NO3, N-NO2, N-NH4, total nitrogen, P-PO4, total phosphorus, organic nitrogen, and organic phosphorus in g/day.
 4. *Discharge* – flow of point source in m³/day
 5. *rho_SS, rho_BOD7, rho_NO3, rho_NO2, rho_NH4, rho_NTOT, rho_PO4, rho_PTOT, rho_NORG, rho_PORG* are the concentrations of suspended solids, BOD7, N-NO3, N-NO2, N-NH4, total nitrogen, P-PO4, total phosphorus, organic nitrogen, and organic phosphorus in mg/l
 6. *year, month* are the calendar year and month.
- d. Variable *PS_YEARLY_CATCHMENT_TABLE* is a file name of MSAccess database and table name where catchmentIDs of pointsources defined by *PS_YEARLY* will be stored.

- e. Variable *PS_YEARLY* contains file name of the table name of yearly pointsource data of those pointsources that are not included in the *PS_MONTHLY_FILE*. This table must contain following fields, the field names are defined in variable *PS_YEARLY_FIELDS*:
 - i. *ID* (integer) - unique id.
 - ii. *year* (integer) – year of pointsource loading.
 - iii. *name* (text) - full name of point source.
 - iv. *type* (integer) – type of point source.
 - v. *nutrient* (text) – type of substance (either of *SS*, *BOD7*, *NO3*, *NO2*, *NH4*, *NTOT*, *PO4*, *PTOT*).
 - vi. *concentration* (double) – value of concentration of corresponding substance in mg/l.
 - vii. *discharge* (double) – value of discharge of pointsource in 1000 m³/y.
 - viii. *X* (double) – x coordinate of point source in coordinates defined by *defcoordSystTxt*.
 - ix. *Y* (double) – y coordinate of point source in coordinates defined by *defcoordSystTxt*.

19. Water users related variables.

- a. *WUS_FILE* contains name of file in PAICSWAT format that contains data about water users. Default value of this variable is **dataDir**+ "*Pointsources/WaterUseMonthly.txt*".
- b. Water users' data consists of two tab delimited text files (*.sta* and *.txt*). Both files should be in the same directory and have the same basename.
 - i. Columns of *.sta* file are: *waterUserID*, *Name*, *X*, *Y*, *sourceID* (*waterUserID* – water user integer ID, *Name* – water user name, *x,y* – water user coordinates, *sourceID* - text identifier of point source that relates water user to point source). Coordinates must be in a coordinate system defined by a variable *defcoordSystTxt*.
 - ii. The file with extension *.txt* contains water usage values. Columns of this file are:
 - 1. *ID* – water user integer ID as defined by *.sta* file.
 - 2. *DATE* – date of point source in *yyyy.mm.dd* format.
 - 3. *WaterUse* – water usage in m³/day

20. Block of the SWAT+ setup related variables (class *SWAT2012DB*).

- a. A weather generator input table must contain field *ID*, that corresponds to station *ID* in *WEATHER_DATA* file. Field *WGN_TABLE* provides location of the schema, tablename and fieldname for station.
- b. *Usersoil* table provides the soil parameters. It must contain soil name field *SNAM*. Variable *USERSOIL_TABLE* provides location of the table.

- c. Crop table provides crop parameters corresponding to the crops and the forest plants in the landuse table. It must contain the crop abbreviation field *CPNM*. Field *CROP_TABLE* provides a location of the table.
 - d. Urban table provides the urban parameters corresponding to the urban landuses in the landuse table. It must contain urban landuse abbreviation field *URBNAME*. Field *URBAN_TABLE* provides a table. Variable *URBAN_PLANT_CODE* provides a crop code from the crop table that will be used for HRUs with urban landuse.
 - e. *cst_user* table stores the information for generating of the weather forecast scenarios (CST). The format of the table is identical to the weather generator input table. The forecast regions correspond to the meteorological stations. Field *CST_TABLE* provides location of the table and fieldname for station.
 - f. Variable *SimulationPeriod* allows the modification of the simulation start year and date, number of years simulated, and a number of years for the simulation warm-up period.
 - g. Variable *defaultCoefficients* provides possibility for the user of the script to enter the default global values of SWAT+ variables. This variable is a python list of tuples. Each tuple consisting of four values:
 - i. type of variables – either “V” if a constant value is entered or “R” if a value relative to initial value is entered. Entering of relative values of the soil coefficients (*SOL* table) and *CN2* coefficient is supported.
 - ii. Name of SWAT+ table.
 - iii. Name of SWAT+ variable.
 - iv. Value of SWAT+ variable.
21. Block of variables related to transboundary inflows from Belarus.
- a. Variable of type Boolean *inflowFromBelarus* determines whether the inflow is taken from measured data (if *False*) or from Belarus SWAT+ model (if *True*). Default value of this variable is *False*.
 - b. Variables *external_Nemunas* and *external_Neris* provide the location of the output files generated by Belarus model for Nemunas and Neris rivers. Variable *externalInflowDir* contains the folder name of Belorussia SWAT+ setup.
 - c. Variable *transBoundaryInlets* is the Python dictionary, containing the list of the identifiers of the external inlets as provided by *TransboundaryInletFile*. For each of the identifiers *stationID* for discharge and water quality stations must be provided. The measured data for these stations from *Q_DATA* and *WQ_DATA* will be used as a transboundary inflow in case if *inflowFromBelarus* is *False*.

2.3. Description of subroutines of script

The following scripts form the renewed modelling system.

2.3.1. Geospatial data processing

All possible geospatial operations are included in and called from *GISoperations.py*. The specific actions (particular scripts) to be run are specified in *main.py*. There are the following steps of the geospatial data processing:

1. Calculation of the catchment centre and area adds the X and Y coordinate of the centre point in LKS_94 (X and Y) and WGS84 (LON and LAT) coordinate systems and area (AREA) to the polygon feature file created during the spatial division of the model

Used script: *catchments.py*, function *CalculateCatchmentCentroidsAndArea()*.

Input/output data: *CatchmentFile*

2. Prepare *RiverNodeFile* table and adds the *nodefrom*, *nodeto* columns to *RiverSegmentFile* table.

Used script: *catchments.py*, function *AddSegmentFirstLastPoints()*.

Input/output data: *RiverSegmentFile*,

Output data: *RiverNodeFile*

3. Calculation and adding the column segment length (LENGTH) to the table created during the spatial division of the model.

Used script: *catchments.py*, function *CalculateSegmentLength()*.

Input/output data: *RiverSegmentFile*

4. Calculation of the river depth either by (1) using a raster provided from the Lithuanian FLOOD project (*riverDepthGrid*) and polygon derived from the grid (*riverFPPolygons*) for the territories covered by the FLOOD project or by (2) using a formula depending on the river basin size. Creating a table for each segment (*segmentdepthtable*).

Used script: *riverdata.py*, function *PrepareRiverData()*.

Input/output data: *riverDepthGrid*, *riverFPPolygons*, *segmentdepthtable* .

5. Calculation of the river width using GDR water polygons (*GDR10LTPolygons*) and creating a table of the river width for each segment (*riverWidthGDR_table*).

Used script: *riverdata.py*, function *PrepareRiverData()*.

Input/output data: *GDR10LTPolygons*, *riverWidthGDR_table*.

6. Joining catchments (*CatchmentFile*) to the hydrological regions (*regionFC*) and adding it to the catchments. The shape file of the hydrological regions of Lithuania is provided by the Client.

Used script: *regionalization.py*, function *PrepareCatchmentRegions()*.

Input/output data: *CatchmentFile*, *regionFC*.

7. Calculation of elevation at the river nodes by extracting DEM (*DEMFile*) values at the nodal points for the calculation of river slopes (*RiverNodeFile*).

Used script: *riverdata.py*, function *ElevationAtNodes()*.

Input data: *DEMFile*, *RiverNodeFile*.

Output data: *nodeElevationFile*

8. Slope calculation from the digital elevation model is done by using script. creating a raster which contains slope values on 5x5 m grid.

Used script: *HRUrasterOps.py*, function *CalculateSlopeRaster*.

Input data: *DEMFile*

Output data: *SlopeFile*

9. First step of HRU delineation creates four rasters with the same resolution and spatial extent as the slope raster *SlopeFile*:

- a. Landuse raster is created using a landuse polygon feature (*LanduseFile*) containing landuse codes and a lookup table (*LUvsSWATTable*) containing a link between the landuse codes and SWAT+ codes found in the SWAT+ crop and urban databases.
- b. Soil raster is created using a soil polygon feature (*SoilFile*) containing soil codes and a lookup table (*SoilvsSWATTable*) which contains a link between the soil codes and SWAT+ codes found in the SWAT+ user_soil database..
- c. Slope-class raster is created using the slope raster (*SlopeFile*, prepared in above step 8) and predefined slope classes (defined in *settings.py.SlopeClasses*).
- d. Catchment raster is created using catchment polygon feature file (*CatchmentFile*) modified in above step 1.

Used script: *HRUrasterOps.py*, function *prepareHRUs* (“Landuse”, ”Soil”, ”Slopeclasses”, ”CatchmentID”)

Input data: *LanduseFile*, *LUvsSWATTable*, *SoilFile*, *SoilvsSWATTable*, *SlopeFile*, *CatchmentFile*.

Output data: *LanduseRasterFile*, *SoilRasterFile*, *slopeClassRaster* and *CatchmentIDRaster*.

10. The second step of HRU delineation intersects the created Landuse, Soil, Slope-class and Catchment rasters using the same Python script as in step 9. It creates a HRU raster (*globalHRUraster*) each cell of which contains a combination of landuse, soil, slope-class and catchment as well as a unique value for each of the combinations. This value defines a single HRU. After this the average slope value for each HRU is calculated and stored in a table.

Used script: *HRUrasterOps.py*, function *prepareHRUs* (“GlobalHRUs”)

Input data: *LanduseRasterFile*, *SoilRasterFile*, *slopeClassRaster*, *CatchmentIDRaster*.

Output data: *globalHRUraster*.

11. Other data which needs to be added to the HRUs are processed creating tables containing the unique HRU identifier and corresponding parameter values:

- a. Melioration data from the melioration polygon feature (*Drainage.TableShapes*) is intersected with every HRU and a value of the fraction meliorated in each HRU is added to a table (*Drainage.HRUDRAINAGE_TABLE*).
- b. County data from the county polygon feature (*countiesFC*) is intersected with every HRU and a value of the county for every HRU added to a table (*countiesHRU*).
- c. Large farm data from the landuse reported data dissolved for farms which are larger than 500ha (*largefarmsFC*) is intersected with every HRU. A cell count of the large farms in each HRU is calculated and a table is created (*hrulargefarms*).

Used scripts: *HRUrasterOps.py*, function *prepareHRUs* (“Drainage”, ”Counties”, ”Regions”), *management.py*, function *prepareLargeFarms()*.

Input data: *globalHRUraster*, *Drainage.TableShapes*, *countiesFC*, *largefarmsFC*.

Output data: *Drainage.HRUDRAINAGE_TABLE*, *countiesHRU*, *hrulargefarms*.

12. The geospatial data which needs to be added at the catchment level is processed:

- a. A polygon feature (*AtmDep.Table_BY_CATCHMENTS*) containing atmospheric deposition values in every catchment is created using the atmospheric deposition data (*AtmDep.TableShapes*) and catchment polygon feature (*CatchmentFile*).
- b. Buffer strip polygon feature *BufferZone.TableShapes* is processed creating a table containing buffer zone statistics in every catchment (*BufferZone.Table_BY_CATCHMENTS*) by intersecting the buffer strip areas with the catchment polygons and calculating the average buffer strip width in the catchment.
- c. Parameter depending on fertilization region (*Fertilizer.TableShape*) is added to each catchment and table for each catchment created (*Fertilizer.TableCoeffByCatchments*).
- d. Hydrological region data from the river basin polygon feature (*regionFC*) is intersected with every HRU and a value of the region for every catchment is added to a table (*tableCatchmentRegion*).
- e. Data about lakes and reservoirs are prepared for each catchment by intersecting the lake and reservoir data (*LakesReserv.TableShapes*) with catchments (*CatchmentFile*) and spatially joined with segments (*RiverSegmentFile*) creating a feature (*lakesreservoirsbycatchments*)

which contains the information about the catchment to which the reservoir or pond belongs and if it is on a modelled reach.

- f. Average annual catchment precipitation is calculated from the annual precipitation raster (*AnnualPrecipitationRaster*) and a table created with a value for each catchment (*catchmentPrecipitationtable*).

Used scripts: *atmosphericdeposition.py*, function *prepareAtmosphericDepositionLayers()*, *bufferstrips.py*, function *prepareBufferStripLayers()*, *lakesReservoirs.py*, function *prepareLakesByCatchments()*, *precipCorrection.py*, function *calcCatchmentPrecipitation()*.
Input data: *globalHRUraster*, *CatchmentFile*, *AtmDep.TableShapes*, *BufferZone.TableShapes*, *Fertilizer.TableShape*, *regionFC*, *LakesReserv.TableShapes*, *RiverSegmentFile*, *AnnualPrecipitationRaster*.
Output data: *AtmDep.Table_BY_CATCHMENTS*, *Fertilizer.TableCoeffByCatchments*, *catchmentsRegions*, *lakesreservoirsbycatchments*, *catchmentPrecipitationtable*.

13. Point sources are assigned to the catchments using the point source data file (*PS_MONTHLY_FILE*) and creating a table which contains the information to which catchment each point source belongs (*PS_catchment_table*).

Used scripts: *pointsources.py*, function *pointSourcesbyCatchments()*
Input data: *PS_MONTHLY_FILE*
Output data: *PS_catchment_table*

14. Landuse updates are prepared for landuse groups per catchment. We use two CORINE landuse polygons (fields *catchments_1*, *catchments_2* of class *LanduseUpdate*). The polygons must contain the defined landuse groups (*LanduseUpdate.groupfield*). A table containing information for a landuse update (*LanduseUpdate.update_fractions*) is created.

Used scripts: *lup.py* function *prepareLUPbyCatchments()*
Input data: *LanduseUpdate.catchments_1*, *LanduseUpdate.catchments_2*
Output data: *LanduseUpdate.update_fractions*

15. The geospatial data processing is finalised by checking whether the Landuse and Soil SWAT+ codes included in the HRU raster (*globalHRUraster*) are found in the SWAT+ database (class *SWAT2012DB*).

Used scripts: *checks.py*, functions *checkLanduseSWATtable*, *checkSoilSWATtable*.
Input data: *globalHRUraster*, *SWAT2012DB*.

2.3.2. Creating SWAT+ modeling system

Rest of the operations for the creation of the SWAT+ model are done without using geospatial tools and mostly includes the creation, filling and updating of SWAT+ parameters in the different SWAT+ Watershed databases.

Figure 2. Spatial object mapping to SWAT+ objects and connections.

Spatial objects, their mapping and connections in SWAT+ are as follows, see Figures 2-3 and Bieger et al (2017):

- Watershed is a set of connected river segments or catchments. It is represented as SWAT+ setup. It may depend on other watershed (upstream rivers). Upstream rivers are represented in SWAT+ as point sources (recalls).
- River segment has one catchment. River segments are represented in SWAT+ as channel.
- Each catchment has the SWAT+ aquifer and landscape unit.

- Each watershed has the SWAT+ deep aquifer.
- Each aquifer is connected to its river segment. Additionally, an aquifer is connected to a deep aquifer.
- Catchments are subdivided into hydrological response units HRU. HRU are connected to the river segment by routing unit (RTU). There is one RTU per catchment.
- Each RTU is connected to the river segment and to the aquifer.

Figure 3. Scheme of SWAT+ objects.

- All routing units within a watershed has the same parameters.
- Ponds and wetlands are represented in SWAT+ catchment as wetlands and connected to a river segment.
- Reservoirs are connected to the first downstream river segment. It is one river segment connected to reservoirs.

The sequential steps of automated model generation are as follows:

1. To start building the databases the model must be split into watersheds and the catchments and rivers must be assigned to them creating the model geometry. For this we need to read all the information required for the creation of the networks. The script *Catchments.py.ReadAll(CatchmentInfo)* is used to read the following data prepared for the further processing:

- a. River segments prepared as a line feature containing information of connection between the river segments and the catchment they belong to as well as the ID to which river belongs (*RiverSegmentFile*) is read.
- b. Nodes are read as point features which correspond to river endpoints (*RiverNodeFile*).
- c. Table containing rivers and their IDs (*RiverTableFile*) for connecting the river names to river segments is read.
- d. Table containing the definition of watersheds, their name and ID (*WatershedTableFile*) is read.
- e. Table containing the connection between catchments and Watersheds including all catchments and the ID of the corresponding Watershed (*CatchmentsByWatershedTableFile*) is read.
- f. Table containing all the outlets of river segments that flow out of the modelling system which includes a unique identifier corresponding to the FlowTo field in the river segment file (*OutletTableFile*) is read.
- g. Table containing all the inlets into the system from transboundary sources containing an ID of the inlet as well as the ID of the river segment it flows into (*TransboundaryInletFile*) is read.
- h. Table containing all the catchments which have a part of their area outside of Lithuania containing the ID of the catchments and area outside of the Lithuanian territory (*TransboundaryCatchmentFile*) is read.
- i. Table containing all special water transfer points (for example, Sanžile canal, Merkys-Voke canal, Gilijos vanal etc.) containing the outletID from which the water is transferred, the river segment to which the water is added and a coefficient by which the amount of water transferred must be multiplied is read.

Used scripts: Catchments.py function ReadAll(CatchmentInfo)

Input data: *RiverSegmentFile*, *RiverNodeFile*, *RiverTableFile*, *WatershedTableFile*, *CatchmentsByWatershedTableFile*, *OutletTableFile*, *TransboundaryInletFile*, *TransboundaryCatchmentFile*.

2. All other information needed for the updating of SWAT+ databases is read:
 - a. Table containing the weather stations for the model including the coordinates (LKS94) and names of the stations .sta file (*WEATHER_DATA*) prepared during weather data processing is read.
 - b. File containing meteorological observations .txt file (*WEATHER_DATA*) prepared during weather data processing is read.

- c. Table of the raster containing the information from HRU delineation (*globalHRUraster*) including Landuse codes, Soil code, cell size of the raster is read. During this procedure processing of the HRUs is performed.
 - i. The HRUs that do not belong to any of catchments are excluded.
 - ii. The HRU with the largest size is found in each catchment.
 - iii. All HRUs smaller than 1 ha are removed, except if there are no HRUs left after this, than the biggest is added.
 - iv. HRU are appended to catchments and the local number in catchment is assigned for each of the HRUs left.
 - v. Calculation of total area of the HRUs left is done.
 - vi. Closest weather station is assigned to each catchment.
- d. Table containing drainage fraction for each HRU (*Drainage.HRUDRAINAGE_TABLE*) created during the processing of geospatial drainage data is read.
- e. Table containing atmospheric deposition in catchments created during the processing of the geospatial data on atmospheric deposition (*AtmDep.BY_CATCHMENTS*) is read.
- f. Table containing the width of the bufferzones in catchments (*BufferZone.Table_STATISTICS_BY_CATCHMENTS*) created during processing of geospatial data on buffer strips is read.

Used scripts: Catchments.py function ReadAll (“HRU”,”METEO”)

Input data: *WEATHER_DATA*, *globalHRUraster*, *Drainage.HRUDRAINAGE_TABLE*, *AtmDep.BY_CATCHMENTS*, *BufferZone.Table_STATISTICS_BY_CATCHMENTS*.

- 3. All Watershed databases are created together with the respective SWAT+ file structure. To do this the following sequential steps are taken using the script *sqliteSetup.py*.
 - a. File structure is created containing the name of the Watershed as the project folder.
 - b. An empty database is created for each Watershed.
 - c. Table structure is copied to empty database from the template database (*swatplus_datasets*).
 - d. *insert_routing_units()* – routing units associated with HRU and LSU are created.
 - e. *FillSolParameters()* - fills the soil parameters from *usersoil* table containing the default parameters for every soil class. River segments are added.

- f. `insert_channels()` - updates channel parameters.
- g. `insert_reservoirs()` - updates reservoir parameters.
- h. `insert_recall()` - monitoring point with the point source type is filled for each river end point (applies monthly point source data to the point sources added to the catchments) and inlets for the Watershed are filled (updates transboundary inlets into SWAT+ setups; the inflows from Nemunas and Neris can be chosen from either the observation data or from SWAT+ model of Belarus).
- i. `insert_hrus()` - HRU tables are filled with the relevant HRU data.
- j. `insert_aquifers()` - aquifer data inserted.
- k. Outflow(connections) of RTU, channel, aquifers and reservoirs are created. `insert_connections()`
- l. `insert_lsus()` - landscape units are created.
- m. `SetSimulationPeriod()` updates the simulation period using the simulation period defined in the `settings.py`.
- n. `FillWeatherTables()` updates the tables related to weather data.
- o. `FillWgn()` updates the weather generator table (Section 2.3) with all the parameters and stations included in the model.
- p. `FillMGTPParameters()` fills default values of `mgt1.cn2` from `usersoiltable`, sets the plant identifier `plant_id` dependent on the landuse and urban tables, sets urban landuse (IURBAN and URBLU) flag for identifying urban territories.
- q. `updateManagement()` fills values for management practices and fertilization.
- r. `updatePrecipCorrection()` fills parameters `RFINC` fields in the `SUB` table by comparing the annual long term precipitation of catchment by the corresponding annual precipitation from the station assigned.
- s. `updateDrainage()` updates drainage parameters depending on the fraction of HRU meliorated, calculates and updates the parameters (`DDRAIN`, `GDRAIN`, and `TDRAIN`).
- t. `updateAtmosphericDeposition()` updates atmospheric deposition parameters according to table (`ATMDEP_BY_CATCHMENTS`) with parameters (`RAMMO_SUB`, `RCN_SUB`, `DRYDEP_NH4`, `DRYDEP_NO3`).

- u. `updateBufferStrips()` updates buffer strip parameter in catchments using the table (*BufzerZone.Table_STAT_BY_CATCHMENTS*).
- v. `SetDefaultCoefficients()` updates coefficient values specified in the `settings.py` files (`defaultCoefficients`).
- w. `updateRegionalCoefficients()` applies the model coefficients by hydrological regions using the table specified in (*REGIONALCOEFFICIENT_TABLE*).
- x. `updateWUS()` updates and applies data for water usage.
- y. `updateLup()` fills land use update coefficients.
- z. `WriteFiles()` writes information from the Watershed database into SWAT+ setup files by calling SWAT+ Editor API (`api/actions/write_files.py`).

Used script: `sqliteSetup.py`, functions `fill_and_write_SWAT_Plus_setups`

Input: *swatplus_datasets*

Output: ready-to-run system of SWAT+ setups.

4. Batch file for the parallelization of the model calculation (sequence of Watershed-by-watershed runs) is created to be allow the run the modeling system in correct order depending on the hierarchy level using the script *prepareRuns.py*.

3. UPGRADE OF DATA

3.1. River network and basin data

3.1.1. Preparation of river network

The river network data (river edges with connectivity information) was updated according to the latest River, lake and reservoir cadaster data version ToR 2.1.1. Missing river network connectivity information for river reaches was established via inspection of aerial photos and satellite information (remote assessment methods), ToR 2.1.2.

The goal of this step was to create the line dataset representing river network. The lines should touch only at their start or end points. Such lines will be called *edges* or *segments* throughout the document. The connection between lines should be provided and it should represent the direction of river flow. The river network was constructed from the supplied river cadaster dataset (*2020-08-17.shp*) that has the cadaster number of the river for each of the lines included in the dataset. The river lines in this dataset are not cut into *edges* and therefore cannot be directly used as a river network. Therefore multiple preprocessing steps were necessary to convert this dataset into line data set that can represent the river network.

The main steps done for preparation of river network are as follows:

1. Initial edge preparation from river cadaster line data. During this step initial *edges* of the river network were extracted from supplied river cadaster line dataset.
 - a. All cadaster river lines were cut at all tributary inflows.
 - b. Missing connections were introduced where feasible.
 - c. Adding of some new river edges were performed, with consecutive changes in adjoint parent edge, now splitted in two new ones, with respective changes to its connectivity.
 - d. Some of a significantly changed river lines were replaced.
 - e. River edges of minor rivers presented in river network from previous project (AAPC&PAIC, 2014) were retained if possible (if didn't cause further contradictions).
2. Preprocessing of edge data consisted of
 - a. Repairing of an invalid geometry.
 - b. Check and repair for intersecting and self-intersecting and overlapping lines.
 - c. Check that all edges should be one line and not multiline.
3. Creating connections between edges of river network. The goal of this step was to provide *river_to* attribute for each of the edges of river network to point in the direction of river flow.
 - a. *river_to* attributes of edges were initially set to ensure that there is no loops in the resulting network. This, however, does not guarantee that

- river network direction at all rivers is correct due to a possible upstream connections between river lines. Therefore, further steps are necessary.
- b. Start and endpoints of edges were snapped to coincide between logically neighbouring edges (according to *river_to* attribute).
 - c. List of sinks – the edges where *river_to* does not point to any other edge – were identified. This allowed to check for internal sinks and possible invalid direction of rivers. This procedure was iteratively repeated for any modification of the river network.
 - d. The diagram of the total count of predecessor edges were constructed – allowing visually identify the parts of the rivers for which the direction was incorrect.
 - e. River network was disconnected at some upstream positions at the watershed divides.
 - f. River network was disconnected at forks that will be represented by *water transfers* (e.g. Levuo-Sanžile channel, Merkys-Voke) in the model.
 - g. Flow directions of rivers were repaired by reversing *river_to* attributes of all edges along the river and fixing *river_to* attributes of inflowing rivers.
 - h. Edge line directions were modified to always be from inflow to outflow. This step simplifies merging of edges when required.
4. Assigning river and lake cadaster information to the edges of the river network
 - a. Lakes with surface area larger than 40 ha were selected from supplied lake cadaster dataset (*2020-08-17_plotiniai.shp*). Resulting dataset was checked for self intersections, the duplicated lake features were found and removed.
 - b. Edges of the river network were split on the boundary of lakes. This is necessary to ensure that no edge intersects lake polygons and resulting edges have unique cadaster ids.
 - c. River cadaster codes (attribute *kadastrid*) were assigned to the edges of the river network. First, the buffered polygon layer with a buffer size 1 meter was constructed from the supplied river cadaster dataset (*2020-08-17.shp*) Intersection between edge lines and this layer were constructed. Resulting cadaster id for a particular edge was selected from the polygon that has the largest intersection length.
 - d. Lake cadaster codes (attribute *kadastrid_lake*) were assigned to the edges of river network. This is done by, first, creating the polygon layer from lakes dataset with negative buffer of 1 meter (this is necessary to ensure that edges flowing into lake but not belonging to it will not have lake cadaster attribute). Then, corresponding lake cadaster attributes were assigned to the edges that intersect this polygon layer.

Figure 4. River network (fine resolution). Colors and line width are styled according to the total area of catchment. Network outlets and water transfer points are depicted.

5. Merging the river *edges* to *segments* representing river and lake cadaster. Merging were done to reduce the number of edges while still representing all rivers included in the river cadaster and all lakes in cadaster with surface area larger than 40 ha
 - a. Some of the *edges* of the river network were marked to further not generate a catchment (attribute *skip_catchment*) while still preserving connection information between edges. Those are (1) some of the edges that represent parts of the rivers that inflow into lake and are located in the lake, (2) some connection which does not represent real rivers (e.g. edges at outflow from reservoirs to downstream river reach), (3) all edges that are shorter than 100 m.
 - b. Network edges are merged into one segment if (1) they have the same river cadaster number (*kadastroid*) and lake cadaster number (*kadastroid_lake*), (2) they do not have any inflows between them, (3) they do not have *water transfer* between them
 - c. Resulting table that stores relation between *edges* and *segments* were prepared.

The resulting segment dataset consists of 11904 segments. The river network is depicted in Figure 4.

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3.1.2. Preparation of catchment polygons

The delineation of the catchment (basin) areas was performed for the river reaches – segment dataset prepared in Section 3.1.1 (ToR 2.1.3) The lake cadaster data (2020-08-17_plotiniai.shp) were used to construct the catchments for both lakes connected to river network and standalone lakes that have water surface area larger than 40 ha (ToR 2.1.4). Basins were assigned to each river water body in a way allowing generate information about water body basin at the exact point where water body begins or ends (ToR 2.1.5).

Delineation of catchments includes the following steps:

1. The delineation was made on a 5 m DEM raster prepared in the previous stage (AAPCS&PAIC, 2014). It was converted into raster tif format located in *Data/DEM/CombinedDEMs/dem_5m.tif*.
2. The DEM raster was modified by strenghtening of the lakes and rivers in it:
 - a. The minimum value of height was calculated for each of the supplied lake polygons (2020-08-17_plotiniai.shp). This value was applied to the raster for each of the corresponding polygons. Resulting raster is *Data/Catchments/Delineation/rasters/DEM_5m_lakes.tif*,
 - b. The river and channel line data from *GDB10LT/product.gdb/Duomenys/HIDRO_L* layer was used to deepen the DEM by 15 m on the river and channel lines. This is necessary to ensure that delineation algorithm can find connections between river segments at the underflows where DEM value is that of the overlying structures (e.g. bridges, dams etc.). We used the line features where value of the corresponding attribute *GKODAS* is not equal to *op01* (imaginary lines, including flows in pipes from reservoir to the downstream reaches). The resulting raster is *Data/Catchments/Delineation/rasters/dem_riversburnedin_5m.tif*.
3. The input raster that contains the initial identifiers of the catchments was prepared:
 - a. The identiers of the river *edges* that are outside lakes were transferred to the raster cells that intersect with corresponding edges
 - b. The lakes were separated into two parts:
 - i. For the lakes that intersect with river edges, corresponding river edge identifiers were distributed over the lake polygons and transferred to the lake cells that intersect with a lake polygon.
 - ii. For the lakes that do not intersect with rivers edges, corresponding lake identifiers (plus offset) in the lake polygons were transferred to the input raster and transferred to the lake cells that intersect with a lake polygon.

4. Delineation by ArcMap hydrology toolset was performed:
 - a. The ArcMap *Fill* tool was used to fill the sinks in a surface raster to remove small imperfections in the data.
 - b. The ArcMap *Flow direction* tool was employed to find flow directions on the raster.
 - c. The ArcMap *Watershed* tool was used to obtain raster containing the catchment identifiers. The inputs for this tool are the flow direction raster and the input point raster.
 - d. The result of delineation is raster containing identifiers of inputs (described in p.3)

5. Merging the identifiers of raster obtained in point 4 to obtain *catchment raster* corresponding to river *segments* (*Data/Catchments/Delineation/rasters/catchm_segmentid.tif*) was done.

6. Catchment raster was converted to the catchment polygons.

7. There are parts of the Lithuania territory that do not correspond to the catchments of any of the prepared segments. They are located near the boundary and are flowing out of Lithuania by streams that are not included in the river cadaster. To find them the catchment polygons obtained in p.6. were subtracted from the polygon of the Lithuania boundary. Resulting polygons were treated in the following way:
 - a. Each of such polygons with the area less than 50 ha was appended to the neighbouring catchment that has the longest common boundary.
 - b. The rest were included in the list of catchments.

8. The connections between the catchments were introduced. In contrary to previous project (AAPC&PAIC, 2014), now there are standalone lakes and possible internal sinks. Therefore, the connections between the catchments should be established even for catchments without the river segments and for the catchments with the river segment that does not flow into any other segment. Attribute *flowto* was introduced into catchment layer; it corresponds to the catchment to which the outflow from a particular catchment is directed. The following steps were made to make the connections:
 - a. For catchments with an outflowing segment *flowto* corresponds to the next catchment downstream the river network. In most cases it is equal to the *riverto* of the corresponding segment, however, it could be different from it, if next segment does not have a catchment (*skip_catchment* is true).
 - b. For standalone lakes, each of the lakes was inspected from remote photographs and the *flowto* was assigned pointing to the direction of flow.
 - c. All internal outlets (*riverto* of corresponding segment equal to -4) were inspected and corresponding *flowto* was assigned.

- d. The list of the outlets was prepared. The outlets correspond to either external outflows or to the water transfers. The *flowto* attribute for the catchments that flow into an outlet was set to -1, and attribute *outletid* contains an identifier of the outlet in this case. Several catchments can have the same *outletid*, specifically, the outlets for the catchments without the corresponding segment were assigned to the closest outlet of a regular catchment.

Figure 5. Catchments (fine resolution). Different catchment types depicted.

9. To find the areas of catchments lying outside the territory of Lithuania, delineation for the territory including all Lithuania, whole Nemunas basin and parts of the other basins were performed using methodology described in points 3,4,5,6.
 - a. We used digital elevation model combining DEM from Belarus from previous project (AAPC&PAIC, 2014) and EU-DEM v1.1⁷ from Copernicus Land Monitoring Service.
 - b. The inputs were prepared for the same edges and lake polygons as described in point 3.
 - c. Resulting catchments polygons corresponding to *segments* were cut by the Lithuania border, leaving only the parts outside Lithuania.
 - d. Corresponding additional area of catchments, except the Nemunas and Neris rivers were calculated and provided in the column *addedarea*.

⁷ <https://land.copernicus.eu/imagery-in-situ/eu-dem/eu-dem-v1.1/view>

Figure 6. Fine catchments inside Lithuania depicted together with corresponding parts of catchments outside of Lithuania.

The resulting catchment dataset consists of 11490 catchments. The catchments according to their types are shown in Figure 5 (for territory of LT) and Figure 6 (adding catchments outside LT).

3.2. Model input data

3.2.1. River network and basins

Model river network and basins data in Section 3.1.2 was renewed corresponding to the latest definition of water bodies (ToR 2.2.7). As water bodies are identified rivers, lakes and reservoirs, which have at least 30 km² upstream basin.

Aggregation of catchment polygons to coarse model polygons was further performed on the river network and fine catchment data prepared in Section 3.1. The goal of this procedure is to obtain aggregated catchments, also referred as *coarse catchments* further throughout the document. The target number of catchments for the whole Lithuania should be approximately the same as in previous project (AAPC&PAIC, 2014).

Figure 7. Catchments and segments for an area in northeast of Lithuania. Fine and coarse catchments, lakes and segments are shown. Coloring by different river and lake cadaster numbers.

1. The procedure proceeds recursively starting from outlets. Each connection between catchments is examined. If there exists at least one inflow from another catchment at the connection where either river or lake cadaster is different and total upstream area of this catchment is at least 50 km² then aggregation border is introduced at this connection. The rest of the catchments are aggregated evenly, their size does not exceed 80 km². All of the fine catchments “flowing” to the same outlet are aggregated according to the same area criteria, therefore most of the fine catchments that were not assigned to a *segment* are incorporated into neighbouring ones.

2. Correspondance table containing identifier of a coarse catchment for each of the fine catchments were prepared. This relation allows to substitute any coarse catchment with all of the fine catchments that it contains. It forms the basis of possibility to model small water basins.
3. The main channel is identified for the aggregated catchments that have segments. The main channel is either
 - a. combination of the segments flowing from inflowing fine catchment to outflowing fine catchment belonging to one coarse catchment; if multiple outflows are present, then the longest path is selected;
 - b. the river with the cadaster number of outflowing fine catchment in case of the upstream catchment without inflow.

The main channel for the catchments forms the segment layer for the coarse catchments.
4. Area and added area for a coarse catchment is the sum of the respective areas for fine catchments that consitute particular coarse catchment

Figure 8. Catchments and segments for an area around Nemunas river in the reservoir of Kaunas HPP. Lakes are also shown. Coloring by different river and lake cadaster numbers. Segments without catchments are marked in red.

Figure 7 shows an area in the northeast part of Lithuania with multiple lakes. The catchments, lakes and segments are depicted, coloring shows distribution of catchments by river and lake cadasters. Each of the lakes greater than 40 ha have an delineated catchment.

Effect of the segments without catchments (*skip_catchment* equals *True*) is shown in Figure 8. Parts of the rivers that flows into the reservoir of the Kaunas HPP and are located within a polygon of HPP are marked as not having catchment.

Figure 9. Catchments and segments in coarse resolution. Lakes with area larger than 40 ha are also depicted.

Resulting dataset of coarse catchments contains 1335 catchments (comparing with 1237 in previous project (AAPC&PAIC, 2014)). Data set of coarse segments contains 1318 segments. Coarse catchments, segments and watersheds are depicted in Figure 9, while fine catchments – in Figures 5-6.

SWAT+ watersheds are composed from coarse catchments, each of them will correspond to one SWAT+ setup. We used watershed definition from previous project (AAPC&PAIC, 2014). Geometric spatial join between coarse catchments from this project and catchments from previous project were performed obtaining table of correspondence of coarse catchments and watersheds. Connectivity of catchments inside each of the watershed were checked, some standalone parts that flow to other watershed were relocated.

3.2.2. Land use

The latest versions of GIS databases were obtained on land use (forest cadastre, crop declaration data, GDR10LT, Mel_DB10LT, SŽNS_DR10LT, AŽ_DR10LT). They were used in preparation of Modeling system (ToR 2.2.5) as described in this Section.

For preparation of landuse data we used similar procedure to previous project (AAPC&PAIC, 2014). There were, however, multiple changes in the formats and fieldnames of data supplied by the Agency. Preparation of combined landuse feature layer was performed by ArcMap software.

The following input data were used:

1. **Declared crops data.** We used declared crops layer for year 2018 as provided by the Client (*SWAT_DATABASE\GIS_DATABASE\Crops\areas_for_declared_crops_2013_2018.gdb\crops2018*). They contain polygonal feature classes, field *KODAS* contains declared field code. Input data were copied for further processing to one feature class stored in *Data/Landuse/landuse.gdb/crops*.
2. **Forest cadaster data.** We used forest cadaster geospatial data as provided by the Client in *SWAT_DATABASE\GIS_DATABASE\Forest\Duomenys_201904.gdb\Sklypas_su_atrib_2019*. It contains polygonal feature classes. We used field *naudmena* representing land use type of forest cadaster lands and *vyr_medz_r* representing dominant tree species. File was preprocessed by removing unnecessary columns and placed in *Data/Landuse/landuse.gdb/forest*.
3. **Abandoned land data.** We used polygonal feature class as provided by the Client in *SWAT_DATABASE\GIS_DATABASE\AZ_DR10LT-1223 2020-08-15 17 35.zip*. No fields from this data source were used. Feature class was copied to *Data/Landuse /landuse.gdb/ abandoned*.
4. **GDR geospatial data** from *GDB10LT* dataset provided by the Client in *SWAT_DATABASE\ GIS_DATABASE\GDB10LT-static-5403 2020-08-15 17 35.zip*. The specification of this dataset is provided in (“GEOREFERENCINIO PAGRINDO KADASTRO ERDVINIŲ DUOMENŲ RINKINIO SPECIFIKACIJA”)⁸, We used polygonal feature class *PLOTAI*, field *GKODAS* represents classification of the geospatial polygons. This feature class was preprocessed by removing unnecessary fields and copied to *Data/Landuse/landuse.gdb/gdr*.

⁸ <https://www.e-tar.lt/portal/lt/legalAct/f9f40a00ec6d11e78a1adea6fe72f3c5>

- There were no new data for **imperviousness**, therefore we used preprocessed imperviousness raster from (AAPC&PAIC, 2014) (*Data/LandUse/Geoland/impervious*).

We used the following preprocessing steps with above input data:

- Spatial union of the declared crops layer, forest cadaster layer, abandoned land layer, and *GDB10LT* layer. Union of above information is a polygonal feature class representing geometric intersection of the input features with all features written. It is located in *Data/Landuse.gdb/union* and contains the fields listed in Table 2.

Table 2. List of fields in unified land use polygons *Data/landuse.gdb/union*.

Field	Contents and exceptions
FID_crops	<i>ObjectID</i> of <i>Data/Landuse/landuse.gdb/crops</i> , -1 if crop is not declared for this polygon
KODAS	<i>KODAS</i> field of <i>Data/Landuse/landuse.gdb/crops</i> representing declared crop code
FID_abandoned	<i>ObjectID</i> of <i>Data/Landuse/landuse.gdb/abandoned</i> , -1 if abandoned land is present in this polygon
FID_gdr	<i>ObjectID</i> in <i>Data/Landuse/landuse.gdb/gdr</i> , -1 if polygon is outside <i>GDB10LT</i>
GKODAS	<i>GKODAS</i> field of <i>Data/Landuse/landuse.gdb/gdr</i> representing polygon class according to <i>GDB10LT PLOTAI</i> feature class
FID_forest	<i>ObjectID</i> in <i>Data//Landuse/landuse.gdb/forest</i> , -1 if polygon is outside forest cadaster data
naudmena	<i>Naudmena</i> field of <i>Data/Landuse/landuse.gdb/forest</i> representing land use type of forest cadaster lands
vyr_medz_r	<i>vyr_medz_r</i> field of <i>Data/ Landuse/landuse.gdb/forest</i> representing dominant tree species
augaviete	<i>augaviete</i> field of <i>Data/ Landuse/landuse.gdb/forest</i> representing soil type of forest lands
Amzius	<i>amzius</i> field of <i>Data/ Landuse/landuse.gdb/forest</i> representing average age of the trees in years
Shape_Length	Perimeter of polygon in m
Shape_Area	Area of polygon in m ²
LUCODE	Generalised land use code for a polygon (see below)

- For the crop types in the declared crops data that were not possible to relate to the crops according to agricultural expert, crop dataset was not used. For those polygons we set *FID_crops* to -1.
- Average imperviousness for the polygons representing *GDB10LT* classes “Build up areas” and “Industrial areas not less than 1 ha” was prepared.

- a. Polygon to raster conversion was performed for the polygons of *union* feature class where *GKODAS* is “pu0” and “pu3”. The resulting raster containing *FID_gdr* values is *Data/LandUse/landuse.gdb/gdr_impervious_raster*.
- b. Zonal statistics tool was used for calculating average value of *Data/LandUse/Geoland/impervious* raster for each unique value of *Data/LandUse/landuse.gdb/gdr_impervious_raster*. Resulting table of the average degree of soil sealing (imperviousness) for each of the polygons is *Data/LandUse/landuse.gdb/gdr_impervious*, field *MEAN*. The ranges of imperviousness for urban land is given in Table 3, they are unchanged from (AAPC&PAIC, 2014)

Table 3. Ranges of imperviousness for urban land use classes.

SWAT urban land use class	Swat name	Degree of soil sealing (imperviousness) from Geoland2
URLD	Residential-Low Density	0% - 18%
URML	Residential-Med/Low Density	18% - 26%
URMD	Residential-Medium Density	26% - 44%
URHD	Residential-High Density	44% - 82%
UIDU	Industrial	82% - 100%

4. We used the rules for land use class generalization (field *LUCODE*)from (AAPC&PAIC, 2014), they are listed below:
 - a. If $FID_crops \geq 0$ (for declared crops), then $LUCODE = "C_"+[KODAS]$.
 - b. Else if $FID_forest \geq 0$ (for forest cadaster data where crops are not declared), $LUCODE = "F_"+[naudmena] + " " + [vyr_medz_r]$. If the value of field *augaviete* is in the list of wet forest soil types (Pa, Pan, Pb) then $LUCODE = "F_"+[naudmena] + " " + [vyr_medz_r] + " " + [augaviete]$
 - c. Else if $FID_abandoned \geq 0$ (for abandoned land without crops declared and not in forest cadaster) then $LUCODE = "A_"$.
 - d. Else if $FID_gdr \geq 0$ and *GKODAS* is neither “pu0” nor “pu3”, then $LUCODE = "G_"+[GKODAS]$.
 - e. Otherwise if $FID_gdr \geq 0$ then $LUCODE = "G_"+[GKODAS] + " " + URBANCLASS$. Urban class is determined from average degrees of soil sealing represented in table *Data/LandUse/landuse.gdb/gdr_impervious*. The ranges of

imperviousness for urban classes are given in Table 3. They are correlated with the values of the range total impervios in Table A-15 of SWAT 2012 I/O manual TWRI (2012).

5. The global lookup table for the connection between the generalized land use code and SWAT code from *crop* or *urban* tables was prepared
 - a. **Declared crops.** We used classification for crop codes provided by the Client in *SWAT_DATABASE\GIS_DATABASE\crops\lu_new_codes.xlsx\croplookup*. There are significant changes in declared crop codes comparing to (AAPC&PAIC, 2014). Table 4 summarizes the respective declared crop classification.

Table 4. Relation of the declared crops classes to SWAT crop classes.

LUCODE	Lithuanian crop name (pasėlis)	Crop name	SWAT code	SWAT crop name
DGP	Daugiametės ganyklos arba pievos 5 metų ir daugiau	perennial pastures	WPAS	Winter Pasture
KVŽ	Žieminiai kviečiai	winter wheat	WWHT	Winter Wheat
KVV	Vasariniai kviečiai	summer wheat	SWHT	Spring Wheat
ŽIR	Žirniai	peas	PEAS	Garden or Canning Peas
RAŽ	Žieminiai rapsai	winter rape	CANA	Spring Canola-Argentine
GPŽ	Ganyklos arba pievos, daugiametės žolės iki 5 metų	perennial pastures for grass production	WPAS	Winter Pasture
MIV	Vasariniai miežiai	summer barley	BARL	Spring Barley
AVI	Avižos	oat	OATS	Oats
PUP	Pupos	beans	GRBN	Green Beans
KRŽ	Žieminiai kvietrugiai	triticale (winter)	WTRC	Winter triticale
PDJ	Juodasis pūdymas	fallow	BARR	Barren
GRI	Grikliai	buckwheat	BWHT	Buckwheat
KUK	Kukurūzai grūdams	corn	CORN	Corn
DOB	Dobilai	clover	ALFA	Alfalfa
RUŽ	Žieminiai rugiai	rye	RYE	Rye
RAV	Vasariniai rapsai	summer rape	SCAN	Summer rape
CUR	Cukriniai runkeliai	sugar beet	SGBT	Sugarbeet

LUCODE	Lithuanian crop name (pasėlis)	Crop name	SWAT code	SWAT crop name
BMI	Žemės ūkio augalų mišiniai, kuriuose baltyminiai augalai yra vyraujantys (išskyrus žolinių augalų mišinius)		LMIX	Mix of legumes with other crops
NMI	Žemės ūkio augalų mišiniai, kuriuose baltyminiai augalai nėra vyraujantys		LMIX	Mix of legumes with other crops
BUL	Bulvės	potato	POTA	Potato
EPT	Ekstensyvus pievų tvarkymas ganant gyvulius		BROS	Smooth Bromegrass
KRV	Vasariniai kvietrugiai	triticale (summer)	STRC	Summer triticale+summer rye
ŽMI	Žolinių augalų mišiniai, kuriuose baltyminės žolės yra vyraujančios (III gr. +GPŽ)		LMIX	Mix of legumes with other crops
MIŽ	Žieminiai miežiai	winter barley	WBAR	Winter Barley
LIC	Liucernos	alfalfa	ALFA	Alfalfa
KMY	Kmynai	caraway	CELR	Celery
PDŽ	Žaliasis pūdymas	fallow	CLVR	Red Clover
KTŽ	Kiti augalai ariamoje žemėje	other agricultural plants	AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
5PT-12	Melioracijos griovių tvarkymas kai žolė bus susmulkinta ir paskleista ant griovio šlaito		BROS	Smooth Bromegrass
OBS	Obelių sodai	apple tree	ORCD	Orchard
NM-4	Kietųjų lapuočių, liepų, selekctinių drebulių (įskaitant hibridines drebulės) grynėji želdiniai	arboretum	POPL	Poplar
ŠAU	Šaltalankių uogynai		ORCD	Orchard
GLU	Gluosnis	willow	WILL	Willow
LUB	Lubinai	lupine	LUPN	Lupine
JSU	Juodųjų serbentų uogynai	black currant	ORCD	Orchard
NM-5	Ažuolų želdiniai, kai želdinamame plote pasodinta ir apsaugota individualiomis apsaugomis ne mažiau kaip 2500 vnt. į ha azuolo sodmenų	arboretum	POPL	Poplar
SJO	Sojos	soy	SOYB	Soybean

LUCODE	Lithuanian crop name (pasėlis)	Crop name	SWAT code	SWAT crop name
MNP	Meldinių nendrinukių buveinių saugojimas natūraliose ir pusiau natūraliose pievose		BROS	Smooth Bromegrass
5PT-3	Ekstensyvus šlapynių tvarkymas		WPAS	Winter Pasture
KAN	Pluoštinės kanapės	Canapis	AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
RZV	Rizikos vandens telkinių būklės gerinimas		WPAS	Winter Pasture
SPT	Specifinių pievų tvarkymas		WPAS	Winter Pasture
NPT	Natūralių ir pusiau natūralių pievų tvarkymas		WPAS	Winter Pasture
KTS	Kiti sodai ir daugiamečiai uogynai		ORCD	Orchard
BRH		rye	RYE	Rye
DAK	Kitos daržovės		CRRT	Carrot
BUR	Burokėliai		CRRT	Carrot
AKM	Azotą kaupiantys augalų mišiniai (susideda tik iš II ir III grupės augalų)		LMIX	Mix of legumes with other crops
FAC	Facelija		LMIX	Mix of legumes with other crops
GAJ	Rudosis, juodosios garstyčios	white mustard	CANP	Spring Canola-Polish
TUO	Tuopa		POPL	Poplar
ALR	Aliejiniai ridikai		CRRT	Carrot
SVO	Svogūnai		CRRT	Carrot
MOR	Morkos		CRRT	Carrot
KOP	Gūžiai kopūstai		CRRT	Carrot
BRA	Braškių uogynai	strawberry	CRRT	Carrot
AVU	Aviečių uogynai	raspberry	ORCD	Orchard
LIN	Linai	flax	AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
BAR	Barkūnai	sweet clover	ALFA	Alfalfa
VIK	Vikiai		VTCH	Vetch
RŠT	Riešutmedžiai		ORCD	Orchard
ARU	Aronijų uogynai		ORCD	Orchard
ŠIU	Šilauogių uogynai		ORCD	Orchard
OŽI	Ožiarūčiai		AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
MOL	Moliūgai		CRRT	Carrot
ESP	Esparcetai		AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown

LUCODE	Lithuanian crop name (pasėlis)	Crop name	SWAT code	SWAT crop name
KRA	Krapai	first-year caraway	CELR	Celery
RUV	Vasariniai rugiai	rye (summer)	SRYE	Summer Rye
AMP	Aromatiniai, medicininiai ir prieskoniniai augalai (mėtos, kalendros, medetkos, čiobreliai, ramunėlės, mairūnai, šalavijai, pankoliai, bazilikai, melisos, valerijonai ir petražolės, raudonėliai kt.)		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
TRS	Trešnių sodai		ORCD	Orchard
5PT-11	Melioracijos griovių tvarkymas kai žolė bus nupjauta ir išvežta		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
ČES	Česnakai		CRRT	Carrot
SRS	Soros	millet	AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
TOP	Topinambai		CRRT	Carrot
JUD	Judra		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
RSU	Raudonųjų serbentų uogynai		ORCD	Orchard
SLO	Salotos		CRRT	Carrot
MNN	Meldinių nendrinukių buveinių saugojimas šlapynėse		CRRT	Carrot
PET			CRRT	Carrot
PAR	Pašariniai runkeliai	common beet	CRRT	Carrot
ŠRM	Šermukšnis		ORCD	Orchard
AGU	Agurkai (uždarajame grunte)		CRRT	Carrot
KRS	Kriaušių sodai		ORCD	Orchard
BRO	Brokoliai		CRRT	Carrot
SLS	Slyvų sodai		ORCD	Orchard
DRA	Drambliažolė		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
ŽM-6	Greitai augančių hibridinių drebulių trumpos rotacijos plantaciniai želdiniai		POPL	Poplar
SVU	Svarainių uogynai		ORCD	Orchard
RAP	Rapsukai		CANA	Spring Canola- Argentine
CUK	Cukinijos		CRRT	Carrot
ŠPA	Šparagai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
NM-6	Greitai augančių hibridinių drebulių trumpos rotacijos plantaciniai želdiniai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown

LUCODE	Lithuanian crop name (pasėlis)	Crop name	SWAT code	SWAT crop name
LEŠ	Lęšiai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
KOK	Kininiai kopūstai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
AGK	Agurkai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
SAU	Saulėgražos		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
5PT-9	Kraštovaizdžio elementų (gyvatvorių) valdoje tvarkymas		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
ŽM-7	Kitų greitai augančių medžių trumpos rotacijos plantaciniai želdiniai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
VYS	Vyšnių sodai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
ERK	Erškėtrožė		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
POM	Pomidorai (uždarajame grunte)		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
SMD	Sausmedis		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
KOŽ	Žiediniai kopūstai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
ASU	Agrastų uogynai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
KLA			AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
ŠPI	Špinatai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
GĖL	Daugiametės gėlės ir dekoratyviniai augalai (uždarajame grunte)		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
DUK	Kitos daržovės (uždarajame grunte)		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
POR	Porai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
RŪG	Rūgštinės		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
RDK	Ridikėliai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
GEU	Gervuogių uogynai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
RID	Baltieji, juodieji ridikai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown

LUCODE	Lithuanian crop name (pasėlis)	Crop name	SWAT code	SWAT crop name
STR	Strypainiai (kanarėlių lesalas)		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
AKT	Aktinidijos		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
SAL	Salierai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
BRU	Braškių uogynai (uždarajame grunte)		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
GRY	Grybai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
ROP	Ropės		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
GUD	Gudobelė		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
BRN			AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
5PT-7	Vandens telkinių apsauga nuo taršos ir dirvos erozijos ariamojoje žemėje		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
KRI	Krienai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
VTP	Vandens telkinių pakrančių apsaugos juostos tvarkymas pievose		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
POD	Pomidorai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
PUU	Putinų uogynai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
LEG			AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
SER	Seradelės		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
GRS	Grybai ir substrato gamyba		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
PAS	Pastarnokai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
GAR	Gargždeniai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
GRE	Griežčiai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
RAB	Rabarbarai		AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
RAD			AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown

LUCODE	Lithuanian crop name (pasėlis)	Crop name	SWAT code	SWAT crop name
SRG	Sorgai		AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
OŽE			AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
SLU			AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
MĖU	Mėlynių uogynai		AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
APY	Apyniai		AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
BAL	Baltalksnis		AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
KAL	Kaliaropės		AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
AGR	Aguročiai		AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
ŽEU	Žemuogių uogynai		AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
KOB	Briuselio kopūstai		AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
NM-7	Kitų greitai augančių medžių trumpos rotacijos plantaciniai želdiniai		AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
SPU	Spanguolių uogynai		AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
PAP	Paprikos		AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
BSU	Baltųjų serbentų uogynai		AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown

b. **Forest lands.** The following rules were used:

- i. If the dominant tree species were defined then we used lookup Table 5 relating these species with the SWAT crop code. There were no additional codes comparing to (AAPC&PAIC, 2014)
- ii. If the soil type corresponds to the wet forests (Pa, Pan, Pb), then the SWAT landuse code was set to *WETF*.
- iii. For other forest lands landuse type was determined using *naudmena* field of forest cadaster data, using lookup Table 6. There were 6 new forest cadaster codes present comparing to (AAPC&PAIC, 2014)

Table 5. Lookup table – relation of dominant species data from forest cadaster to SWAT crop classes.

vyr_medz_r	name_Lithuanian	SWATCODE	CROPNAME
P	Pušis	PINE	Pine
Pb	Pušis bankso	PINE	Pine
Pk	Pušis kalninė	PINE	Pine
Pj	Pušis juodoji	PINE	Pine
E	Eglė	FRSE	Forest-Evergreen
Pc	Pocūgė	FRSE	Forest-Evergreen
Kn	Kėnis	FRSE	Forest-Evergreen
M	Maumedis	FRSE	Forest-Evergreen
Ks	Kiti spygliuočiai	FRSE	Forest-Evergreen
Kk	Kiti kietieji lapuočiai	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous
A	Ažuolas	OAK	Oak
Ar	Ažuolas raudonasis	OAK	Oak
U	Uosis	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous
K	Klevas	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous
Sb	Skroblas	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous
G	Guoba	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous
S	Skirpstas	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous
B	Beržas	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous
Bt	Baltalksnis	POPL	Poplar
J	Juodalksnis	POPL	Poplar
D	Drebulė	POPL	Poplar
T	Tuopa	POPL	Poplar
L	Liepa	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous
Bl	Blindė	WILL	Willow
Gl	Gluosnis	WILL	Willow
Km	Kiti minkštieji lapuočiai	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous
Kd	Kedras	FRSE	Forest-Evergreen
V	Vinkšna	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous
Bu	Bukas	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous

Table 6. Lookup table – relation of forest land use classes to SWAT crop/urban classes.

Naudmena	Name_Lithuanian	SWATCODE	CROP/URBAN
5	Kirtavietė	BARR	Barren
6	Žuvęs medynas	BARR	Barren
7	Miško aikštė	BARR	Barren
8	Žemė, skirta miškui įveisti	BARR	Barren
9	Miško žemė, verčiama ne miško	WPAS	Winter Pasture
10	Daigynas	RNGB	Range-Brush
11	Medelynas	RNGB	Range-Brush
12	Sėklinė plantacija	RNGB	Range-Brush

Naudmena	Name_Lithuanian	SWATCODE	CROP/URBAN
13	Žaliavinė plantacija	WILL	Willow
14	Rekreaciniai želdiniai	WILL	Willow
20	Kvartalinė	BARR	Barren
21	Technologinė linija	WPAS	Winter Pasture
22	Priešgaisrinė juosta	BARR	Barren
23	Griovio trasa	WPAS	Winter Pasture
24	Elektros trasa	WPAS	Winter Pasture
25	Ryšių trasa	WPAS	Winter Pasture
26	Energetikos trasa	WPAS	Winter Pasture
28	Elektros linija	WPAS	Winter Pasture
29	Miško kelias	UTRN	Transportation
30	Priešgaisrinis barjeras	BARR	Barren
31	Medienos sandėlis	BARR	Barren
32	Miško poilsiavietė	FRST	Forest-Mixed
33	Pašarų aikštelė	FRST	Forest-Mixed
34	Miško laukymė	WPAS	Winter Pasture
35		WETF	Wet forest
36		WETF	Wet forest
37		WPAS	Winter Pasture
9	Miško žemė, verčiama ne miško	WPAS	Winter Pasture
40	Ariama žemė	AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
41	Pieva	WPAS	Winter Pasture
42	Ganykla	WPAS	Winter Pasture
43	Sodas	ORCD	Orchard
45	Krūmai	RNGB	Range-Brush
47	Pelkė	WETL	Wetlands-Mixed
50	Pastatai	URMD	Residential-Medium Density
51	Sodyba	URLD	Residential-Low Density
52	Kiemas	URMD	Residential-Medium Density
53	Paminklinė aikštė	URMD	Residential-Medium Density
54	Geležinkelio pylimas	UTRN	Transportation
55	Kelias	UTRN	Transportation
60	Ežeras	WATR	Water
62	Kūdra	WATR	Water
63	Tvenkinys	WATR	Water
64	Griovys	WATR	Water
70	Trasa (platesnė nei 10 m.)	WPAS	Winter Pasture

Naudmena	Name_Lithuanian	SWATCODE	CROP/URBAN
74	Karjeras	BARR	Barren
75	Poilsiavietė	BARR	Barren
76	Paplūdimys	BARR	Barren
77	Kopos	BARR	Barren
78	Skardis	BARR	Barren
79	Akmenynas	BARR	Barren
80	Kapinės	URLD	Residential-Low Density
81	Durpynas	BARR	Barren
82	Smėlynas	BARR	Barren
83	Kitos žemės	RNGB	Range-Brush
84	Parkas	FRST	Forest-Mixed
85	Skveras (aikštė)	FRST	Forest-Mixed
86	Sodas (botan., zool.)	FRST	Forest-Mixed
87	Dekoratyvinis želdynas	ORCD	Orchard
88	Žalioji jungtis	WPAS	Winter Pasture
89	Sąvartynas	UIDU	Industrial
91	Žemė, apauganti mišku	FRST	Forest-Mixed

- c. For abandoned lands we used SWAT crop code *RNGB* representing range brush.
- d. The classification (relation) of GDB10LT classes according to SWAT crop/urban codes is given in Table 7. For Build-up areas urban class was determined from imperviousness according to Table 3. There were 11 new GDB10 codes necessary comparing to (AAPC&PAIC, 2014)

Table 7. Connection of GDR10LT landuse classification with SWAT crop/urban classes.

GKODAS	SWATCODE	CROP/URBAN
gt12	UTRN	Transportation
gt14	UTRN	Transportation
gt15	UTRN	Transportation
gt16	UTRN	Transportation
gt18	UTRN	Transportation
gt19	UTRN	Transportation
gt2	UTRN	Transportation
hd1	WATR	Water
hd2	WATR	Water
hd21	WATR	Water
hd22	WATR	Water
hd23	WATR	Water
hd3	WATR	Water

GKODAS	SWATCODE	CROP/URBAN
hd4	WATR	Water
hd5	WATR	Water
hd6	WETL	Wetlands-Mixed
hd9	WATR	Water
ms0	FRST	Forest-Mixed
ms4	ORCD	Orchard
pu0	determined by imperviousness	
pu3	determined by imperviousness	
sd11	AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
sd15	RNGB	Range-Brush
sd2	WPAS	Winter Pasture
sd4	BARR	Barren
sd42	BARR	Barren
sd7	BARR	Barren
va1	URLD	Residential-Low Density
va11	UTRN	Transportation
vk1	URLD	Residential-Low Density
vp1	URLD	Residential-Low Density
ed0	WETL	Wetlands-Mixed
ek0	WATR	Water
gt17	UTRN	Transportation
mj0	RNGB	Range-Brush
ms4	ORCD	Orchard
va12	UTRN	Transportation
vg1	UIDU	Industrial
vg2	UIDU	Industrial
vg3	BARR	Barren
vg31	BARR	Barren
ms0hd6	WETF	Wet forest

Figure 10. Illustration of land use polygons near Kaunas.

The illustrations of the prepared land use data are shown in Figures 10-11.

The prepared data (landuse polygons and lookup tables) were transferred to PostGIS tables under the Postgre schema landuse to be used by the modelling system scripts.

Figure 11. Illustration of the land use polygons. Small scale detalisation.

3.2.3. Soil

The latest version of GIS database on soil (Dirv_DB10LT) was obtained and used in renewal of Modeling system (ToR 2.2.5) following the methodics of the previous project (AAPC&PAIC, 2014). There were new soil data and forest cadaster data inputs. Some of the field names in input data were different.

The following input data was used:

1. **Soil data from database *DIRV_DB10LT*** as provided by the Client in *SWAT_DATABASE\GIS_DATABASE\Dirv_DR10LT-1571_2020-08-15_1739.zip*. Polygon feature class *konturas* was used. Field *SNS_KOMI_T*, representing systematic soil type code, soil granulometric content and texture codes (further referred as *SoilCode*) was used. Field *PAVKOMPI* shows soil code. If the soil code is missing then symbol ‘M’ in this field means forest, ‘SV’ urban territories, while ‘W’ is water. The database file was preprocessed by removing unnecessary columns and placed in *Data/Soil/soil.gdb/dirv*.
2. **Forest cadaster data.** We used forest cadaster geospatial data as provided in *SWAT_DATABASE\GIS_DATABASE\Forest\Duomenys_201904.gdb\Sklypas_su_atrib_2019*. It contains polygonal feature classes. Field *augaviete* is required to determine the soil type in the forest. File was preprocessed by dissolving polygons using *augaviete* field. It is placed in *Data/soil/soil.gdb/forest*.
3. **Quaternary geology data** represented by polygon feature class is taken from preprocessed data layer of previous project (AAPC&PAIC, 2014). Fields *INDEKSAS* representing geological index and *LITOLOGIJA* representing name of the soil lithology were used. We used column *LITOINDEX* representing an index of soil lithology that was done in previous project using forest soil lookup table (see below p.5). The intermediate file is placed in *Data/Soil/geology/quaternary_geology.shp*.
4. **Soil maps** on scale 1:300000 was taken from previous project (AAPC&PAIC, 2014) The file is copied to *Data/Soil/Soil_300000/soil.shp*. Field *SNS* representing systematic soil type code was used from these maps.
5. **Forest soil lookup table** as provided by soil expert in (AAPC&PAIC, 2014). We placed it in *Data/soil/soil.gdb/forestsoillookup*. Field *Aug_G_gr1* were used representing composite index: “forest soil + geological index + lithological index”. It provides a link between the forest *augaviete* field combined with geological and lithological indices and *SoilCode* represented by field *Dirv_gran*.

6. **Lookup table for soil aggregation** relating *SoilCode* and aggregated soil code (further referred to as *SWATSoilCode*). Main part of it was taken from (AAPC&PAIC, 2014). There were 64 new *SoilCode* values comparing to the lookup table of the previous project. We supplemented aggregation lookups for them. Lookup table was placed in *Data/soil/soil.gdb/globallookup* and in the Postgre schema *soil*, table *globallookup*.
7. **Soil properties' table** for aggregated soil types of SWAT model was taken from the previous project.

Figure 12. Illustration of soil polygons. Coloring by soil group.

We used the following processing steps with above input data:

1. Geospatial union of various data sources: soil data polygons (*DIRV_DB10LT*), forest cadaster polygons, quaternary geology polygons and reduced scale soil polygons. Result of this union is a polygon feature class placed in *Data/soil/soil.gdb/union* and in the Postgre schema *soil*, table *union*.
2. Assigning *SoilCode* field for the resulting unified set of polygons as follows (applying the below steps in decreasing priority):
 - a. If a field *SNS_KOM1_T* is not empty, then *SoilCode* = *SNS_KOM1_T* (data from *DIRV_DR10LT*).

- b. Assign composite key combining “forest soil + geological index + lithological index” (fields: *augaviete*, *INDEKSAS*, *LITOINDEX*) to the polygons. If the composite key is present in the forest soil lookup table then *SoilCode* = *Dirv_gran*.
- c. If a systematic soil type code is present in the soil maps on scale 1:300000 (field *SNS* is not empty) then *SoilCode* = *SNS*.

An illustration of the soil polygons is shown in Figure 12.

3.2.4. Atmospheric deposition data

The latest available atmospheric deposition data from EMEP⁹ was used in the renewal of Modeling system (ToR 2.2.3). Results of the EMEP model are provided on 0.1 degrees grid. Latest available gridded data for the yearly values of deposition were downloaded - year 2018 (2017 emissions) and placed in *Data/AtmosphericDeposition/EMEPData/EMEP01_rv4_35_year.2018met_2018emis.nc*.

Following preprocessing steps were made:

1. Subset of EMEP data was selected for longitudes between 20.5°E and 27.5°E and latitudes between 53.5°N and 57°N
2. Necessary variables were selected (see Table 8).
3. Data were converted from the raster cells to rectangular polygons for later use by modelling script. Data was placed in GeoJson file *Data\AtmosphericDeposition\Data\AtmDep2018.geojson*, corresponding Postgre table *atmdep2018* were placed under the schema *atm_deposition*.

Table 8. Atmospheric deposition variables.

Variable, unit	EMEP field name	Preprocessed data field name
Yearly precipitation, mm	WDEP_PREC	precipitation
Dry deposition of reduced nitrogen, mgN/m ² /year	DDEP_RDN_m2Grid	NH4_dry
Wet deposition of reduced nitrogen, mgN/m ² /year	WDEP_RDN	NH4_wet
Dry deposition of oxidised nitrogen, mgN/m ² /year	DDEP_OXN_m2Grid	NO3_dry
Dry deposition of oxidised nitrogen, mgN/m ² /year	WDEP_OXN	NO3_wet

Figures 13-15 show distribution of the wet and dry deposition of the reduced (NH₄) and the oxidised (NO₃) nitrogen.

⁹ https://www.emep.int/mscw/mscw_ydata.html

Figure 13. Yearly amount of dry deposition of reduced nitrogen.

Figure 14. Yearly amount of wet deposition of reduced nitrogen.

Figure 15. Yearly amount of dry deposition of oxidised nitrogen.

Figure 16. Yearly amount of wet deposition of oxidised nitrogen.

3.2.5. Meteorological data

Meteorological data of the stations of the existing Modelling system were extended with the data of 2013-2019 supplied by the Agency. The meteorological data input from Lithuanian meteorological agency (LHMT) was supplied by the Client in the PAICSWAT format (*SWAT_DATABASE\MEASURED\Model Overwrite\Data_Observations\weatherdata.txt*). There are no new stations in the supplied data (see Figure 17 for the map of the observation stations).

The nomenclature of the meteorological parameters consists of daily mean temperature (T, degrees C), minimal daily temperature (Tmin, degrees C), maximal daily temperature (Tmax, degrees C), precipitation (P, mm/day), wind speed (W10, m/s), relative humidity (RHUM, %) and solar radiation (SLR, MJ/day/m²),

Figure 17. Locations of agroclimatic weather data stations and the monitoring stations of LHMT.

The datafiles were copied to:

- Table containing the weather stations for the model including the coordinates (LKS94) and names of the stations *Data\Meteo\Hidromet\weatherdata.sta*.
- File containing meteorological observations *Data\Meteo\Hidromet\weatherdata.txt*.

Availability analysis for each of the stations and parameters for each of the calendar years was performed to check feasibility of data for the model input. The availability of daily precipitation, daily mean, minimal and maximal temperature, daily wind speed

and daily mean relative humidity are excellent with minimal exceptions and are valid for input into modelling system, see Figures 18-24.

The solar irradiance data in the previous project (AAPC&PAIC, 2014) was available in two stations – Kaunas and Šilutė. Present supplied data additionally has coverage for year 2017 at every station and coverage for the recent years at Vilnius, Biržai and Nida. It is not particularly clear whether solar irradiance data for a single year 2017 is obtained from the direct measurements. We propose to use only data from Kaunas and Šilutė as solar irradiance input.

The yearly average parameters were calculated for each of the stations and calendar years (see Figures 32, 36-40, 43). This allows us to evaluate feasibility of data comparing to data in (PAIC, 2014). There are no significant outliers at any of yearly statistical parameters. It means that newly supplied data could be used for input in the modelling system.

Figure 18. Availability of daily precipitation.

Figure 19. Availability of daily mean temperature.

Figure 20. Availability of daily maximal temperature.

Figure 21. Availability of daily minimal temperature.

Figure 22. Availability of daily mean wind speed.

Figure 23. Availability of daily mean relative humidity.

Figure 24. Availability of daily mean solar irradiance.

Meteorological data from Lithuanian Agriculture Advisory Service was considered for the use with Modelling system according to ToR 2.2.1.

Meteorological data from these agoclimatic stations were obtained by Fieldclimate API¹⁰ provided by Pessl Instruments GmbH. Access to this api requires public and private HMAC keys supplied by the Client. Supplied private key is tied to a particular set of stations, corresponding to the agroclimatic stations in Lithuania. The url of the root of the Fieldclimate API is <https://api.fieldclimate.com/v2>

We did the following steps to get the data:

1. The list of all stations were obtained by querying the “*List of user devices*” API (<https://api.fieldclimate.com/v2/docs/#user-list-of-user-devices>). We converted obtained JSON file of station metadata and placed in *Data/Meteo/Agroclimatic/fieldclimate_stations.xlsx*. The station coordinates are in the field *position.geo.coordinates*, the station identifiers are in the field *name.original* and the station names are in the field *name.custom*. The rest of the fields are not necessary for our purpose. There are 76 agroclimatic stations available. The locations of the stations are shown in Figure 17.
2. We queried the API for the daily values of meteorological parameters for the period 2005-2020. We used “*Get data between period*” query (<https://api.fieldclimate.com/v2/docs/#data-get-data-between-period>). The data for each of the stations from p.1 for each of the year was requested. Multiple types of sensor data are returned for each of the stations. We used the sensor type summarised in Table 9 that correspond to the daily meteorological data necessary for SWAT+ input.

Table 9. Sensor identification parameters in Fieldclimate system.

Variable	Modeling system abbreviation	Fieldclimate sensor group	Fieldclimate sensor code	Fieldclimate aggregation id
Daily mean temperature	T	1	506	avg
Daily maximal temperature	Tmax	1	506	max
Daily minimal temperature	Tmin	1	506	min
Daily precipitation	Prec	5	6	sum
Daily mean windspeed	W10	5	6	avg
Daily mean relative humidity	RHUM	2	507	avg
Daily mean solar irradiance	Solar	4	600	avg

¹⁰ <https://api.fieldclimate.com/v2/docs/>

3. Conversion of the units for the solar irradiation was performed from W/m^2 to $MJ/m^2/day$ as necessary for SWAT+ input.
4. Data for each of the stations was combined and saved in *Data/Meteo/Agroclimatic/data/{stationid}.xlsx*. File that contains all the data for all stations was also prepared in *Data/Meteo/Agroclimatic/data/all.xlsx*.
5. Initial filtering of the data was performed, the data which exceeds 150 units was discarded. Result were placed in *Data/Meteo/Agroclimatic/data/all_filtered.xlsx*.
6. Agroclimatic data series was converted also in PAICSWAT format for further use in modelling system, These files are *Data/Meteo/Agroclimatic/agroclimatic.sta*, *Data/Meteo/Agroclimatic/agroclimatic.txt*, *Data/Meteo/Agroclimatic/agroclimatic_filtered.sta*, *Data/Meteo/Agroclimatic/agroclimatic_filtered.txt*

Figure 25. Availability of daily precipitation at agroclimatic stations for the years 2007-2020.

Figure 26. Availability of daily mean temperature at agroclimatic stations for the years 2007-2020.

Figure 27. Availability of daily maximal temperature at agroclimatic stations for the years 2007-2020.

Figure 28. Availability of daily minimal temperature at agroclimatic stations for the years 2007-2020.

Figure 29. Availability of daily mean windspeed at agroclimatic stations for the years 2007-2020.

Figure 30. Availability of daily mean relative humidity at agroclimatic stations for the years 2007-2020.

Figure 31. Availability of daily mean solar irradiance at agroclimatic stations for the years 2007-2020.

The quality assesment of the agroclimatic data was performed after the data acquisition.

1. First, the percentual availability of each variable for each of the stations for each calendar year was performed (see Figures 25 – 31). Availability of the data is generally rather low, except for year 2020 (that is not included in the model calculation period). There are only 8 stations with have some coverage with precipitation measurements for the years 2007-2019, although satisfactory availability (>95%) is for only some of the years. Availability of daily wind speed and solar irradiance is approximately the same as for the precipitation, while availability for mean, maximal and minimal daily temperature is significantly lower. The conclusion from the availability study is that it could be possible to use only selected years for selected stations as input data for modelling.

Figure 32. Yearly sums of precipitation (mm) for agroclimatic and LHMT stations.

2. The possibility to use the agroclimatic stations' data was further assessed via the statistical analysis of the yearly mean values for the years with availability that are larger than 95% and compared them to the same statistical values for the data from the observation stations by LHMT (see Figures 32, 36-40, 43). To qualify for use with model, the yearly means of data from the agroclimatic stations should be close to the range of the yearly means for the LHMT stations.

Figure 33. Measured data series of daily precipitation. No data during winter periods.

Figure 34. Measured data series of daily precipitation. Example of “zero value” for “no value”.

- a. There are multiple years for multiple stations with precipitation sums significantly lower or higher than that of LHMT stations (Figure 32). Additional problems are
 - i. There are no precipitation measurements during winter periods (see Figure 33) in several stations.
 - ii. Further, for part of the period with high availability of data (e.g. whole year 2019) there are zero value instead of no-value (Figure 34).
 - iii. There could be intermittent/irregular invalid values and spikes of possibly invalid values in the data series that could be hard to distinguish from the valid ones (see Figure 35)

Figure 35. Measured data series of daily precipitation – irregular/intermittent invalid values (years 2018, 2019).

Figure 36. Yearly mean temperature (°C) for agroclimatic and LHMT stations.

Figure 37. Yearly mean daily maximal temperature (°C) for agroclimatic and LHMT stations.

- b. Daily mean and mean of daily minimal temperatures of LAAS stations are in the range of the LHMT stations (Figures 36, 37) while the mean values of the daily maximal temperature in LAAS stations are on average higher than that of LHMT stations (Figure 38).
- c. The yearly wind speed is significantly lower for all years at all agroclimatic stations comparing to the yearly mean wind speed at LHMT stations (Figure 39).
- d. There are many distinct outlier years for some of the stations concerning mean relative humidity (Figure 40). Besides that the quality problems were identified as:
 - i. There are “zero values” of parameter instead of “no-value” or “wrong value”, see Figure 41.
 - ii. It could be that the sensors of the meteo stations are switched thus polluting the otherwise valid data series, see Figure 42.

Figure 38. Yearly mean daily minimal temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) for agroclimatic and LHMT stations.

- e. The yearly means of solar radiation for some of the agroclimatic stations are very different, comparing to rather low range of mean solar irradiance measured at LHMT stations, see Figure 43. There are some spikes of potentially invalid values that are hard to distinguish from valid ones, see Figure 44.

The conclusion from the yearly mean value study is that even for the years with sufficient data coverage, there are incorrect data in the data series of agroclimatic stations that significantly modify the yearly mean value statistics. Examining the data series we identified several error patterns. It means that without thorough quality assesment it is not possible to use the daily series of measured meteorological parameters at the LAAS agroclimatic stations. Such quality assesment is out of scope of the present project.

Figure 39. Yearly mean wind speed (m/s) for agroclimatic and LHMT stations.

Figure 40. Yearly mean relative humidity (%) for agroclimatic and LHMT stations.

Figure 41. Measured data series of daily mean relative humidity. Illustration of intermittent periods where zero value are measured (should be no-value/wrong value).

Figure 42. Measured data series of daily mean relative humidity – potentially switched sensor channels in the year 2014.

Figure 43. Yearly mean solar irradiance ($\text{MJ}/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$) for agroclimatic and LHMT stations.

Figure 44. Measured data series of daily mean solar irradiance – there are some spikes of potentially invalid values that are hard to distinguish from the valid ones.

3.2.6. Water use and pollution point sources

Wateruse data should was updated with 2013-2019 data for points, which are in the existing Modeling system (ToR 2.2.2).

The point source data was preprocessed for the automated usage in the generation of the water quality modeling system. Similarly to (AAPC&PAIC, 2014) all the point sources were divided into two parts:

1. The large pollution sources for which the point sources loads were prepared im the monthly temporal resolution.
2. The rest of the pollution point sources were prepared as the time series of yearly pollution values.

Point source preprocessing was done separately for the point source data until the year 2012 (data from previous project) and starting from 2013 (new data). After preprocessing both datasets (each consisting of monthly and yearly parts) were combined into a joint dataset.

The preprocessed point source data for the period before 2013 were taken from (AAPC&PAIC, 2014). The files are placed under the *Data/Pointsources/Preprocessing/Data2014*. They consist of

1. *Monthly.sta* and *Monthly.txt* files representing the large pollution sources up to and including the year 2012.
2. *Small_PointSources.mdb* for the rest of pollution sources up to and including the year 2012.

Following steps were taken for preparing the point source data for the new period (2013-2019):

1. The intermediate files containing information about the monthly discharges until the year 2016 (including) was supplied by the Client (directory *SWAT_DATABASE\MEASURED\Model Overwrite\Data_PointSources\srcDATA*):
 - a. *WQ.dat* (monthly water discharge data);
 - b. *QWQ.dat* (monthly water quality data);
 - c. *WWTP_Stations* (list of biggest city water treatment plants with identifiers and names).
2. The yearly point source data for the new period were prepared as follows:
 - a. Data sources were yearly pointsource data file provided by the Client in directory *SWAT_DATABASE\MEASURED\wwtp\from_2013*, files *2013.csv*, *2014.csv*, *2015.csv*, *2016.csv*, *2017.csv*, *2018.csv*, *2019.csv*.
 - b. We used the script *point_source_prep.py* that was provided by the Client. We modified it (included in *Data\Pointsources\Preprocessing\PS_SCRIPT\Scripts\point_source_p*

rep.py). The purpose of this script is to rename the columns according to new data, to harmonise the identifiers of WWTP types with the ones in the previous project, and to separate large point sources. The outputs of the script are

- i. the yearly point source data for the stations included in *WWTP_Stations*, file *Data\Pointsources\Preprocessing\PS_SCRIPT\DATA_OUT\000_yearly_ins.csv*
 - ii. the yearly point source data for the stations that is not included in *WWTP_Stations*, file *Data\Pointsources\Preprocessing\PS_SCRIPT\DATA_OUT\000_Small_PointSources_ins.csv*
3. The large pollution sources with monthly discharge values (as listed in *WWTP_Stations* file, see p.1) were processed as follows:
- a. The missing pollution components were filled in this data using the methodics of AAPC (2008), Table 1.2.2. Namely, if missing then (1) total nitrogen was calculated form BOD₇, (2) total phosphorus was calculated form BOD₇, (3) the inorganic nitrogen forms were calculated form total nitrogen.
 - b. The gaps shorter as 3 months in monthly values were filled by interpolation.
 - c. The yearly values were filled in the intermediate data (p.3f below) filling with data all months of the year for which data is available in the database.
 - d. The monthly values (p.3b above) were filled in the intermediate data.
 - e. The rest of the intermediate data was filled with the average values.
 - f. Thus, the full (all monthly values, all substances) intermediate dataset was formed. It included 2 files (directory *Data/Pointsources/Preprocessing*):
 - *Monthly.sta* file containing: *pointsourceID*, *Name*, *X*, *Y*, *sourceID* (*pointsourceID* – point source integer ID, *Name* - point source name, *X,Y* - point source coordinates, *sourceID* - text identifier of point source that relates it to the original data).
 - *Monthly_new.txt* contains monthly point source values. Columns of this file are:
 - *ID* – the point source integer ID as defined by *.sta* file.
 - *DATE* – date of point source in *yyyy.mm.dd* format. Day for monthly point sources is always 15.

- *SS, BOD7, NO3, NO2, NH4, NTOT, PO4, PTOT, NORG, PORG* are the loads of suspended solids, BOD7, N-NO3, N-NO2, N-NH4, total nitrogen, P-PO4, total phosphorus, organic nitrogen, and organic phosphorus in g/day.
- *Discharge* – flow of point source in m³/day
- *rho_SS, rho_BOD7, rho_NO3, rho_NO2, rho_NH4, rho_NTOT, rho_PO4, rho_PTOT, rho_NORG, rho_PORG* are the concentrations of suspended solids, BOD7, N-NO3, N-NO2, N-NH4, total nitrogen, P-PO4, total phosphorus, organic nitrogen, and organic phosphorus in mg/l
- *year, month* are the calendar year and month.

4. The rest of the pollution point sources were prepared as the time series of yearly pollution values (see p.2.b.ii).

Figure 45. Total load of N-NO3 in tonnes/year from point sources in Lithuania territory.

Combining of the point source data of the previous period (until 2012 including) and the new period (2013-2019) was done as follows:

1. For the large point sources corresponding *Monthly.sta* and *Monthly.txt* files (see above) were combined. Result are in *Data\Pointsources\monthly.sta*, *Data\Pointsources\monthly.txt*.
2. For the rest of the point sources we combined data from the previous period located in *Data\Pointsources\Preprocessing\Data2014\Small_PointSources.mdb* with the data from the new period (see p.4 above). Resulting data are in csv format (file *Data\Pointsources\Small_PointSources.txt*).

Figures 45 and 46 show the time graph of the total nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus loads from the point sources using the input data prepared according to the described methodology. Total load is distinguished between “large point sources” and “the rest of point sources”.

Figure 46. Total load of P-PO4 in tonnes/year from point sources in Lithuania territory.

We used water use data file supplied by the Client in *SWAT_DATABASE\MEASURED\Model Overwrite\Data_PointSources\srcDATA\Water_Use.txt*. It consists of yearly water usage and WWTP plant code for the whole period. We made a lookup of WWTP code against WWTP code from previous project, converted to water use text files according to format in previous project (AAPC&PAIC, 2014). Two text files were created (directory *Data/Pointsources*):

1. *WaterUseMonthly.sta* contains columns: *waterUserID*, *Name*, *X*, *Y*, *sourceID* (*waterUserID* – water user integer ID, *Name* – water user name, *x,y* – water user coordinates, *sourceID* - text identifier of point source that relates water user to point source).
2. *WaterUseMonthly.txt* contains the water usage values. Columns of this file contain *ID* (water user integer ID as defined in *sta* file), *DATE* (date of point source) and *WaterUse* (water usage in m³/day).

3.2.7. Fertilization data

Fertilization data was updated according to the information delivered by the Agency (ToR 2.2.4). Methods of calculating applied fertilisation, fertilisation modelling approach and methods used were not changed from the existing system (AAPC&PAIC, 2014).

Updated information that was provided and used:

- Soil database (Dirv_DR10LT) actual to date 2020-08-15
- Crop yields (up to 2019)
- Farm animal numbers (up to 2020)
- Declared crop database (up to 2018)
- Declared crop database plants to SWAT codes

The following data and definitions were updated to evaluate required amount of mineral fertiliser depending on the crop, location (region of Lithuania) and soil.

- 1. Soil data** – Soil database provided by the Client was used (Dirv_DR10LT) up to date at 2020-08-15, parameters used in methodics were not changed:
 - a. Aggregated soil name. Identified in soil data as *AGR_IBY-ID*;
 - b. Content of clay particles, %. Identified in soil data as *SOL_CLAY1*;
 - c. Organic carbon content, %. This parameter is used for humus content evaluation. Identified in soil data as *SOL_CBN*;
 - d. Soil phosphorus content, mg/kg. Identified in soil data as *SOL_SOLP1*;
 - e. Soil acidity, Ph. This parameter was provided by the soil expert (AAPC&PAIC, 2014) in addition to parameters from soil data. It is identified in soil data as *SOL_PHI*.
- 2. Plant data** – data for updating these values was provided by Client and updated in the system:
 - a. SWAT ID – SWAT land use identifiers corresponding to agricultural plants some new plant codes were introduced, see Section 3.2.2 “Land use”.
 - b. Calculation method – 2 methods were used for fertiliser amount assessment as before in (AAPC&PAIC, 2014);
 - c. Standard yield, t/ha – plant standard yield, provided only for those crops for which the 1st calculation method was used. In cases when it is missing the 2nd method was used and also it was assumed that standard yield is equal to planned yield.
 - d. Standard nitrogen demand, kg/ha – standard nitrogen demand for specific plant. It corresponds to standard yield or in cases when the standard yield is not provided to a planned yield.
 - e. Standard phosphorus demand, kg/ha – standard phosphorus demand for specific plant. It corresponds to a standard yield or in cases when standard yield is not provided to a planned yield.

- f. Nitrogen amount in soil after preplant of particular plant – in cases where a preplant is not known, it was assumed that this value is 0;
- g. Phosphorus amount in soil after preplant of particular plant - in cases where a preplant is not known, it was assumed that this value is 0.

3. Crop yield data was provided by Client and updated in the system :

- a. Plant ID – plant codes. Multiple crops may correspond to each of SWAT crop IDs.
- b. Planned Yield, t/ha – data of plant yield depends on both plant and municipality (region of Lithuania).

Table 10. Representative crop names in statistical data for SWAT+ crop codes that employ method 1 for fertilization calculation. Average planned yields from (AAPC&PAIC, 2014) and present project are included

SWATCODE	Representative crop name in statistical data	Average planned yield, (AAPC&PAIC 2014), t/ha	Average yield, statistics 2001-2019, t/ha
ALFA	Dobilų ir jų mišinių šienas	2.92	3.10
BARL	Vasariniai miežiai	2.60	2.58
OATS	Avižos	1.97	2.15
PGWF	Daugiamečių žolių iki 5 metų šienas	1.83	2.83
POTA	Bulvės, išskyrus ankstyvasias	13.24	13.63
RYE	Žieminiai rugiai	2.29	2.39
SCAN	Vasariniai rapsai	1.49	1.61
SGBT	Cukriniai runkeliai (perdirbimui)	27.38	33.91
SRYE	Vasariniai rugiai	2.29	2.16
SWHT	Vasariniai kviečiai	2.70	2.92
WPAS	Daugiamečių žolių iki 5 metų šienas	1.83	2.83
WTRC	Žieminiai kvietrugiai	2.69	2.85
WWHT	Žieminiai kviečiai	2.94	3.45

Planned crop yield is necessary for the calculation of fertilisation by method 1 (see AAPC&PAIC, 2014). For updating the necessary data we used a following method:

1. The crop yields on the district level from the department of statistics *SWAT_DATABASE\MGT\crop_yields_1990_2019.csv* provided by the Client was used.

2. The provided data contains yield of different crops on a yearly basis at each of the administrative units. To avoid double accounting, we filtered out the aggregated administrative divisions (“Sostinės regionas”, “Vidurio ir vakarų Lietuvos regionas”, “Lietuvos Respublika” and all divisions where code \leq 10 (“apskritis”).
3. For all SWAT crop codes that employ method 1 for fertilization calculation, representative crops from the statistical data were chosen (see Table 10).
4. Average crop yields for selected representative crops were calculated for each of the districts for the time period 2001-2019.
5. Planned yield for each of the counties is equal to that of the district to which the county belongs.
6. For districts that does not have corresponding statistical data for particular crop, the average yield for this crop over all other districts was used (see also Table 10, column 4).
7. The resulting data is placed in *Data\CropData\planned_yield.csv*. Its fields are:
 - a. *SWATCODE* – SWAT+ crop code
 - b. *countyid* – identifier of the county
 - c. *planned_yields* – planned yield in t/ha

Figure 47 shows an example of the planned yield distribution for winter wheat (WWHT).

Figure 47. Planned yield of winter wheat (WWHT).

- 4. Livestock data.** In (AAPC&PAIC, 2014) the historical data on the **livestock** amount per county was used. To update it we employed the data about the farm animals on a district level (“savivaldybe”) that were provided by the Client in *SWAT_DATABASE\MGT\farm_animals_1991_2020.csv*.

The following methodology was employed:

1. The provided data contains count of different animal groups on a yearly basis at each of the administrative divisions. To avoid double accounting the following filtering was necessary:
 - a. Filter-out aggregated administrative divisions (“Sostinės regionas”, “Vidurio ir vakarų Lietuvos regionas”, “Lietuvos Respublika” and all divisions where code≤10 (“apskritis”).
 - b. Filter out aggregated animal groups (see Table 11).
2. For each of the animal types a standard animal unit value was assigned from the EC guidelines¹¹, see Table 11.
3. For each of the districts and years total amount of livestock units were found by multiplying amounts of particular animals with the livestock units from Table 11 and summing up.
4. Average value of livestock units for each of the districts was calculated for two periods: (2001-2012) – “previous period” and (2001-2019) – “total period”.
5. The ratio between livestock units of “total period” and “previous period” were calculated for each of the districts.
6. The lookup table between counties and districts was used (*Data\Counties\Counties.shp*). For each county belonging to a particular district the same ratio from p.5 was used.
7. The livestock data from previous project (AAPC&PAIC, 2014) on a county level (provided in *Data\CropData\PreviousProjectResultingTables\FertCalcddata.xlsx*, sheet *Livestock_data*) was multiplied by a corresponding ratio. Resulting livestock data is placed in *Data\CropData\livestock_by_county.xlsx* for further use by modelling system. See the livestock distribution on county level in Figure 48.

¹¹ [https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Glossary:Livestock_unit_\(LSU\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Glossary:Livestock_unit_(LSU))

Table 11. Animal names from livestock statistics and assigned livestock units. Unused aggregated groups are marked.

Animal name in Lithuanian	Livestock unit
Antys	0.03
Arkliai	0.8
Avys	0.1
Bičių šeimos	0
Buliai 2 metų ir vyresni	1
Buliukai ir telyčaitės skersti iki 1 metų	0.4
Buliukai nuo 1 iki 2 metų	0.7
Buliukai veislei iki 1 metų	0.4
Galvijai, iš viso	Aggregated group
Kalakutai	0.03
Karvės (melžiamos 2 metų ir vyresnės)	1
Karvės žindenės 2 metų ir vyresnės	1
Karvės, išskyrus melžiamas ir žindenes	0.8
Kiaulės	Aggregated group
Kumelės 3 metų ir vyresnės	Included in "Arkliai"
Ožkos	0.1
Paršeliai 20–50 kg (2–4 mėn.)	0.3
Paršeliai iki 20 kg (iki 2 mėn.)	0.027
Paukščiai, iš viso	Aggregated group
Paukščiai, išskyrus vištas, žąsis, antis ir kalakutus	0.03
Penimos kiaulės 50–80 kg (4–6 mėn.)	0.3
Penimos kiaulės 80–110 kg (6–8 mėn.)	0.3
Penimos kiaulės virš 110 kg (8 mėn. ir vyresnės)	0.3
Telyčaitės veislei iki 1 metų	0.4
Telyčios skersti 2 metų ir vyresnės	0.8
Telyčios skersti nuo 1 iki 2 metų	0.7
Telyčios veislei 2 metų ir vyresnės	0.8
Telyčios veislei nuo 1 iki 2 metų	0.7
Triušiai	0.02
Vedeklės ir jauneklės ožkos 1 metų ir vyresnės	Included in "Ožkos"
Veisliniai kuiliai virš 50 kg	0.5
Veislinės nesukergtos kiaulaitės virš 50 kg	0.5
Veislinės pagrindinės paršavedės virš 50 kg	0.5
Veislinės pakaitinės paršavedės virš 50 kg	0.5
Veislinės sukergtos kiaulaitės virš 50 kg	0.5
Vištos dedeklės	0.014
Vištos, iš viso	0.007 for "Vištos, iš viso"- "Vištos dedeklės"
Ėriavedės ir jauneklės avys 1 metų ir vyresnės	Included in "Avys"
Žąsys	0.03

Figure 48. Amount of livestock per county in livestock units.

3.2.8. Change in land use

Based on previously and newly gathered GIS data update, .lup files were prepared to account for the land use change processes in the renewal of Modeling system (ToR 2.2.6).

The CORINE¹² 2006 and CORINE 2018 data sets were used to account for changes in land cover. The following method was used:

1. The land use classes are aggregated in 7 groups as “Agricultural”, “Pastures”, “Forest”, “Urban”, “Wetlands”, “Water” and “Barren”.
2. For each of the catchments the relative fractions of each of the group of the land use classes are calculated for CORINE 2006 and CORINE 2018.
3. The table containing catchment ID, and 7 numbers – the changes (in %) of the relative fraction of each of the group of land use classes was prepared.

The prepared data is further used by the automated system of the generation of the water quality modeling system for creation of .lup files of respective SWAT+ subbasins.

¹² <https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover>

3.2.9. Drainage data

Drainage data is updated according to ToR 2.2.5. The methodology is unchanged from (AAPC&PAIC, 2014). The structure of input data provided by the Agency, however, is changed significantly. The update of the data was implemented as follows:

Figure 49. The drained polygons according to melioration database.

1. Updated version of melioration cadaster data was supplied by the Client in *SWAT_DATABASE\GIS_DATABASE\MEL_DR10LT-1836 2020-08-15 17 31.zip*. The structure of supplied melioration cadaster data is different comparing to previous project.
2. We used layer *MELPLOT_P* from the supplied database. This layer contains the polygon data of the meliorated territories and field attributes including type of the drainage. Contrary to the previous project this layer does not contain the status of melioration system. Field *GKODAS* of this layer contains code of the type of drainage system (hm0 – drained by drains, hm0g – drained by ditches). Only areas drained by drains (*GKODAS = hm0*) were considered.
3. The drainage system with the bad status are stored in the layer *BUKLE_P*. This layer overlaps the *MELPLOT_P* layer at some places, but is provided on different polygons.
4. The written-off melioration systems are provided in *NURAS_P* layer. This layer intersects *MELPLOT_P* layer at some places, but at some places it does not cover the *MELPLOT_P* layer.

5. We neglected the status of melioration systems as in the previous project (AAPC&PAIC, 2014).
6. The output was constructed by selecting polygons from *MELPLOT_P* where *GKODAS='hm0'* and dissolving resulting features (see Figure 49). The resulting data is placed in *Data\MeliorationDb\melioration.shp* and copied to table *melioration* under the schema *meldr10_lt* for the use by modelling system.

4. MODELLING SMALL WATER BODIES

The updated river network data prepared in Sections 3.1. and 3.2.1 was used for the building a Modelling system in the spatial resolution of the small river water bodies corresponding to the entries in the river, lake and reservoir cadaster, thus creating the modelling capabilities for small water bodies (ToR 1.2.1). The spatial division of this “fine resolution” model is shown in Figures 5-6.

The Python scripts in the renewed Modelling system (Chapter 2) are prepared for the automatic preparation of the model setup for small water bodies (ToR 1.2.2).

As a result, TWO systems of watersheds and SWAT+ setups are prepared (and updated):

- “Coarse (regular) spatial resolution”, corresponding to the resolution of existing modelling system AAPC&PAIC (2014), see the resolution in Figure 9.
- “Fine spatial resolution” corresponding to the modeling of small water bodies, Figures 5-6.

Both model resolutions may be compared in Figures 7-8.

The input file *list_fine_resolution* is aimed for user defined list of the catchments (by catchment ID), for which the modelling in fine resolution is intended. Running the model automatically selects the catchments of the watershed in either of “fine” or “coarse” resolutions, according to user’s preference given in this file (ToR 1.2.4). Thus, the integration of small water body setup within the rest of Modeling system is achieved (ToR 1.2.3). Prepared script/s allows user to select any small river water body or their list and preparing, running model and providing output is done automatically with possibility to define required output and time step (ToR 1.2.4).

Since the modelling system in fine resolution is created independently (not derived from the coarse) then it automatically complies with requirements of ToR 1.2.5 (compatibility of output files with PAICSWAT, ToR 1.2.6 (handling of model parts in neighbouring countries) and ToR 1.2.7 (handling the lakes and reservoirs).

5. RAINFALL RADAR DATA

The precipitation radar data from two radar stations (Laukuva and Vilnius) was supplied by the Agency in h5 (“support.hdfgroup.org/HDF5/doc/H5.format.html”) format for two time periods from 30-Sep-2020 04:00 until 16-Oct-2020 20:00 and from 21-Oct-2020 07:00 until 24.10.2020 16:00.

The sum of precipitation for previous 24 h was included in the files on either 254x254 cell grid (Sep-2020, cell size 1972 m) or 586 x 493 cell grid (Oct-2020, cell size 819 m).

The sample of radar data is shown in Figure 50 for 30-Sep-2020, 04:00.

Figure 50. Rainfall pattern from radar stations Laukuva (left) and Vilnius (right). 30-Sep-2020 04:00.

Figure 51. Biržai: radar measurements vs. observations. Daily precipitation in mm.

Let us compare the precipitation observations in hydrometeorological stations with the radar data. Note that the grid of the radar at Laukuva doesn't cover Dūkštas, while the grid of radar at Vilnius doesn't cover Klaipėda and Nida.

Hourly time series of radar data (each data point is the sum of precipitation during previous 24 h) are compared with the observations (daily sums of precipitation) in Figures 51-68.

Figure 52. Dotnuva: radar measurements vs. observations. Daily precipitation in mm.

Figure 53. Dūkštas: radar measurements vs. observations. Daily precipitation in mm.

The comparison indicates that – in general – there is a good coincidence of precipitation between the observations and radar data; further – there is a reasonable correlation between both radars in the overlapping stations.

However, the radar data always provide lower precipitation values in comparison with the observations. This is summarized for both radars and all observation stations in Table 12. For the all period of observations the difference in the total amount of precipitation is 50% for both radars.

Figure 54. Kaunas: radar measurements vs. observations. Daily precipitation in mm.

Figure 55. Kybartai: radar measurements vs. observations. Daily precipitation in mm.

Further, we noticed that the discrepancy between the radar and observation data increases with the station's distance from the radar. These distances are also summarized in Table 12.

The absolute difference between the observation and radar data is shown in Figure 69 as function of the distance between the radar and the observation station. The Figure shows that (1) the difference between the radar and the observations may be quite significant even for the stations located close to the radar; (2) the “radar error” significantly increases for the stations located more then 150 km from the radar.

Figure 56. Klaipėda: radar measurements vs. observations. Daily precipitation in mm.

Figure 57. Laukuva: radar measurements vs. observations. Daily precipitation in mm.

Figure 58. Lazdijai: radar measurements vs. observations. Daily precipitation in mm.

Figure 59. Nida: radar measurements vs. observations. Daily precipitation in mm.

Figure 60. Panevėžys: radar vs. observations. Daily precipitation in mm.

Figure 61. Raseiniai: radar vs. observations. Daily precipitation in mm.

Figure 62. Šiauliai: radar vs. observations. Daily precipitation in mm.

Figure 63. Šilutė: radar vs. observations. Daily precipitation in mm.

Figure 64. Telšiai: radar vs. observations. Daily precipitation in mm.

Figure 65. Ukmergė: radar vs. observations. Daily precipitation in mm.

Figure 66. Utena: radar vs. observations. Daily precipitation in mm.

Figure 67. Varena: radar vs. observations. Daily precipitation in mm.

Figure 68. Vilnius: radar vs. observations. Daily precipitation in mm.

Table 12. Comparison of total rainfall in period from 01-Oct-20 until 16-Ocr-2020.

	Total precipitation, mm			Distance from the radar, km	
	Laukuva	Vilnius	Obs	Laukuva	Vilnius
Biržai	16.3	14.1	52.8	171	177
Dotnuva	24.3	26.6	29.5	106	124
Dūkštas		30.7	45.3	257	118
Kaunas	24.6	27.4	33.4	130	97
Kybartai	26.1	21.1	45.2	115	161
Klaipėda	33.5		56.1	75	295
Laukuva	23.2	6.8	40.6		223
Lazdijai	15.9	31.5	47.2	175	123
Nida	38.5		76.0	84	284
Panevėžys	17.1	21.4	32.8	136	137
Raseiniai	20.8	15.8	25.9	62	162
Šiauliai	16.3	9.2	38.5	77	191
Šilutė	23.4	1.3	45.0	57	257
Telšiai	21.3	2.4	38.2	39	243
Ukmergė	16.1	24.1	36.0	165	76
Utena	9.6	45.2	45.6	213	102
Varėna	6.4	17.1	38.6	213	64
Vilnius	7.7	21.1	33.4	223	

Figure 69. Distance from the radar (km) vs. absolute error in rainfall (mm) for the both radars and all meteorological stations.

The performed analysis (ToR 1.3.4) indicates that the precipitation radar data cannot be directly used as the input data for the water quality modelling system; there exist both underestimation of the precipitation in the radar data and the increase of this difference with the distance from the radar. These conclusions hold for both radars under consideration.

According to the ToR 1.3.1-1.3.3 the Python script radar.py is developed which:

- Reads the specified set of radar data files
- Reads the list of centers of Modelling system catchments
- Generates *.pcp files for these catchments or updates the existing (specified) *.pcp files with the radar data.

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ANNEX: Electronic deliverables

Modelling system

The water quality modeling system is electronically delivered as a data archive. Un-archiving of it creates a folder structure in **MAINPATH**. The water quality modeling system is generated automatically by executing the script *main.py* from folders **projectDir /Scripts**.

River network and catchment data

The feature datasets of the prepared river network and catchment data are located under PostGre schema *catchmentdata*. Following data tables are included:

1. River network segment dataset for fine resolution – *segments_fine*. The fields are:
 - a. *id* – the identifier of segment
 - b. *riverto* – the identifier of segment to which particular segment flows. Special values: -1 – external outflow, -4 – internal outflow.
 - c. *skip_catchment*. Whether this segment has corresponding catchment
 - d. *kadastruid* – river cadaster id, that corresponds to field *kadastruid* in supplied river cadaster dataset (*2020-08-17.shp*)
 - e. *kadastruid_lake* – lake cadaster id, that corresponds to field *kadastruid* in supplied lake cadaster dataset (*2020-08-17_plotiniai.shp*)
 - f. *length* – the length of segment in meters
 - g. *geometry* – the PostGIS geometry column, representing segment. All segments are of geometry type *ST_LineString*

2. Catchment polygon dataset for fine resolution – *catchments_fine*. The fields are:
 - a. *id* – identifier of the catchment
 - b. *type* – type of catchment. Possible values are:
 - i. 1 – catcment having segment without the lake
 - ii. 2 – catcment having segment and the lake
 - iii. 3 – catchment having only standalone lake
 - iv. 4 – catchment without segment or lake
 - c. *segmentid* – identifier of segment for catchments of types 1 and 2, otherwise blank. If supplied is equal to *id*.
 - d. *lakegid* – identifier of lake for catchments of types 2 and 3, otherwise blank. It corresponds to attribute *gid* of lake cadaster dataset.
 - e. *kadastruid* – river cadaster id, that corresponds to field *kadastruid* in supplied river cadaster dataset (*2020-08-17.shp*)
 - f. *kadastruid_lake* – lake cadaster id, that corresponds to field *kadastruid* in supplied lake cadaster dataset (*2020-08-17_plotiniai.shp*)
 - g. *flowto* – identifier of catchment to which outflow is directed. -1 for outlets
 - h. *segmentto* – corresponds to *riverto* of segment, for types 1 and 2m otherwise blank

- i. *outletid* – identifier of outlet for catchments flowin into outlets, including water transfers
 - j. *area* – area of catchment in m², excluding area outside Lithuania
 - k. *addedarea* – area of catchment that lies outside Lithuania, except for catchments having inflow from Nemunas and Neris
 - l. *inflowarea* - area of catchment that lies outside Lithuania, for catchments having inflow from Nemunas and Neris
 - m. *geometry* – the PostGIS geometry column, representing catchment. They have PostGIS geometry type *ST_Polygon* or *ST_MultiPolygon*
3. Outlet dataset – *outlets*. Fields are:
 - a. *id* – identifier of the outlet
 - b. *outlettype* – type of outlet. 3 – outlet is water transfer, other values – external outlet
 - c. *outletname* – name of the outlet
 4. Water transfer dataset – *transfers*. Fields are:
 - a. *id* - identifier of transfer table entry
 - b. *outletid* – identifier of outlet
 - c. *name* - name of water transfer entry
 - d. *flowto* – catchment receiving outflow from this water transfer entry
 - e. *multiplier* – outflow to inflow ratio for this water transfer entry
 5. Catchment polygon dataset for coarse resolution *catchments_coarse*. The fields are the same as for dataset for fine catchments
 6. Segment polygon for coarse resolution *segments_coarse*. The fields are the same as for dataset for segments of fine resolution
 7. Data table that contains correspondance map between catchments of fine and coarse resolution *map_coarse_fine*. Fields are:
 - a. *id* – identifier of fine catchment
 - b. *group* – identifier of coarse catchment
 8. Table of watersheds – *watersheds*. Fields are:
 - a. *watershedid* – identifier of watershed
 - b. *basinname* – name of watershed basin
 - c. *watershedname* – name of watershed
 - d. *composite* – composite
 9. Data table containing correspondance map between coarse catchments and watersheds *coarse_catchm_wsh*. Fields are:
 - a. *catchmentid* - identifier of catchment
 - b. *wshid* – identifier of watershed

10. Data table containing correspondance map between fine catchments and watersheds *fine_catchm_wsh*. Fields are:
 - a. *catchmentid* - identifier of catchment
 - b. *wshid* – identifier of watershed

Land use

Following layers are transferred to PostGIS tables under the Postgre schema *landuse* to be used by the modelling system scripts:

1. *landuse* – contains landuse polygons. Fields are:
 - a. *objectid* – identifier of landuse polygon
 - b. *lucode* - generalized landuse code as described in point 4 of this chapter
 - c. *shape_area* – area of polygon in m²
 - d. *shape_length* – perimeter of polygon in m
 - e. *shape* – PostGIS geometry columns
2. *globallookup* – table for connection of *landuse.lucode* with SWAT+ crop/urban codes. Fields are:
 - a. *globalcode* – generalized landuse code corresponding to field *lucode* of table *landuse*
 - b. *swatcode* – SWAT+ crop or urban code

The following additional electronic data is supplied:

1. *lucode_statistics* – summary areas of *union* polygons grouped by *LUCODE*
2. *crops_statistics* – summary areas of *crop* polygons grouped by *DKL_PASEL*
3. *forest_statistics* – summary areas of *forest* polygons grouped by *naudmena*, *vyr_medz_r*, *augaviete*
4. *gdr_statistics* – summary areas of *GDR* polygons grouped by *GKODAS*.

Other input data

For soil data, atmospheric deposition, meteorological data, wateruse and point source data, fertilisation (incl livestock) data included in the electronic deliverables see the respective sections of the report.